

Post-Fiscal Inequality in India

Constructing a Lived Income Gini, 2014 - 2025

Vidhu Shekhar¹ and Surabhi Mukhopadhyay¹

¹SPJIMR, Vidhu Shekhar, Associate Professor, Surabhi Mukhopadhyay,
Research Analyst

April 10, 2026

Abstract

This paper develops a fiscal-incidence-based measure of post-intervention household inequality in India by integrating survey evidence, tax-return statistics, and the monetised value of welfare transfers. It constructs a hybrid income distribution using a log-normal specification for the bottom 90 percent and a Pareto tail for the top decile, and then estimates the equalising effect of taxes, subsidies, and public provisioning on household command over resources.

Keywords: inequality, fiscal incidence, India, Gini coefficient, welfare transfers, redistribution

JEL Classification: D31, H22, H23, I38

1. Introduction

India, a democratic and welfare-oriented state, is often surrounded by concerns regarding inequality, be it income inequality (as depicted by World Inequality Lab's Income Inequality estimate of 0.61 [World Inequality Database, 2025c]) which depicts a highly unequal income hierarchy or consumption inequality (0.25 [World Bank, 2025c]) which often draws its own share of criticism for being too optimistic. The WIL inequality metric (or Gini Index) may, however, be empirically overstated owing to its choice of methodological framework. Its estimates are grounded in an income distribution that excludes personal income taxes and government redistribution, instead employing a pre-tax, pre-transfer income metric [World Inequality Database, 2025a]. This approach treats the distributive impact of fiscal interventions, whether through progressive taxation or targeted welfare schemes, as analytically of less relevance, thereby offering only a partial view of the states role in promoting a more equitable society. Consequently, the redistributive impact of policy is rendered invisible within the data.

A related measurement issue is addressed, in part, by OECD inequality indicators, which incorporate cash transfers, taxes, and formal social insurance into post-fiscal income estimates [OECD, nd]. These measures capture redistribution when it passes through documented fiscal channels and is recorded in conventional household income data. For instance, Germany's pre-tax WIL Gini estimate is 0.49 [World Inequality Database, 2025b], whereas its OECD post-tax income Gini is 0.29 [Federal Government of Germany, nd], indicating a substantial reduction in measured inequality. In this sense, OECD-style Gini are designed to register the equalising effects of fiscal policy. In India, however, a considerable share of welfare provision operates through institutional channels that are only partially reflected in standard income-based inequality measures. Subsidised food, cooking fuel support, housing assistance, public health insurance, nutrition programmes, sanitation, and water infrastructure may materially expand household command over resources without appearing fully in conventional Gini estimates. Recent fiscal incidence work has sought to address this limitation. Bhalla, Bhasin, and Virmani (2022) [Bhalla et al., 2022] show that accounting for in-kind government support, especially food subsidies, lowers measured deprivation and inequality, while Kundu and Cabrerias (2022) application of the Commitment to Equity framework to India [Kundu and Cabrera, 2022] finds that taxes, transfers, and public spending on education and health generate a meaningful compressive effect on the distribution. Taken together, this literature suggests that conventional inequality statistics may understate the redistributive effects of the Indian welfare state.

This study reconstructs the income distribution and accounts for the role of the state in the analysis. It combines large-scale survey data (PLFS) to represent the bottom 90 percent of households with tax-return data to capture the highest earners, ensuring that both ordinary households and the top income groups are properly represented. The overall distribution is modelled using a two-part structure, Log Normal Distribution for the broad middle and lower population, and Pareto Distribution for the high-income tail, consistent with DINA-based approaches used in inequality research. The Pareto tail index is estimated using the local inter-bracket exponent from the ₹25–50 lakh range of the ITR distribution, consistent with the Generalised Pareto Interpolation technique employed in the DINA framework, and converted to a household-level parameter using an approximate 4/3 compression multiplier. The regime threshold x_m is set at the 90th percentile of the modelled household income distribution, ensuring that Decile 10 represents exactly the top 10 per cent of households. Market incomes are then expanded to include the money value of welfare support provided through government schemes. These benefits are valued conservatively using actual government spending, insurance claims, and annualised housing assistance rather than maximum entitlements. Further, we distribute a consolidated welfare budget of ₹17.05 Lakh Crores using a “Targeted Inverse Consumption” weighting mechanism. This approach assigns transfers inversely to Monthly Per Capita Expenditure (MPCE), ensuring that the poorest decile receives the highest support while the richest decile is methodologically excluded. We simultaneously deduct direct tax liabilities from the top decile alone in order to reflect the statutory structure of the Indian tax base.

The quantitative verdict of this analysis reveals that the Indian fiscal state produces substantial inequality compression. The intervention reduces the Gini coefficient by 24.7%, bringing it down from the market baseline of 0.348 to a final Lived Income Gini of 0.262. This reduction is driven by an asymmetric intervention: the poorest 10% of households

receive a targeted transfer of ₹1.17 Lakhs, effectively increasing (+88%) their annual purchasing power, while the top 10% see their disposable income contract by -6.6% due to tax liabilities and exclusion from welfare benefits.

The study also undertakes a temporal comparison across three fiscal years to assess whether the redistributive capacity of the Indian fiscal system has strengthened or stagnated over the past decade. Applying the identical methodological framework to FY 2014-15, FY 2017-18, and FY 2024-25, the analysis finds that both pre-fiscal and post-fiscal inequality declined monotonically across all three periods, with the post-fiscal Gini falling from 0.306 to 0.285 to 0.262. The redistribution ratio, defined as the proportional compression between the market and lived income Gini, rose from 17.5 per cent to 19.8 per cent to 24.7 per cent over the same interval. This progressive strengthening occurred even as the pre-fiscal baseline itself declined from 0.371 to 0.348, a condition under which further compression requires proportionally greater fiscal effort. The acceleration is attributable in part to the introduction of three entirely new programmatic instruments after 2018 and in part to the near-tripling of the per-household welfare transfer from ₹22,908 to ₹63,136 over the decade.

These findings point to a measurable divergence between market-generated inequality and the inequality of lived outcomes. The gap between the pre-fiscal Gini (0.348) and the post-fiscal Lived Income Gini (0.262) indicates that the fiscal system absorbs a non-trivial share of market disparity before it translates into household consumption. It bears noting, however, that the Gini coefficient is a measure of relative dispersion rather than of absolute living standards; two distributions may yield comparable Gini values while differing materially in the welfare they afford at each point of the distribution. The fiscal sustainability of this trajectory, the adequacy of the welfare architecture in addressing dimensions of deprivation that extend beyond consumption, and the extent to which behavioural responses may attenuate the measured incidence over time constitute open questions that warrant examination in subsequent work.

2. Conceptual Background

India exhibits one of the widest divergences between income-based and consumption-based inequality estimates observed in any major economy. Income Gini coefficients reported in the literature exceed 0.6, while consumption-based estimates cluster near 0.25. This divergence reflects, in substantial part, the different objects being measured. Income metrics record market outcomes - wages, profits, rents, and returns to capital - prior to government intervention. Consumption metrics record household expenditure after market income, transfers, subsidies, savings decisions, and public provisioning have already interacted. The two approaches consequently answer different questions and need not be expected to converge.

Each approach carries its own limitations for the purpose of fiscal incidence analysis. Income-based measures typically exclude in-kind transfers and public service provisioning, leaving a significant portion of government redistribution unobserved. Consumption-based measures incorporate these effects implicitly but do not permit attribution to specific fiscal instruments, since the individual contributions of taxation, transfers, and pri-

vate savings are already embedded in the observed expenditure. The analytical challenge, accordingly, is to construct a framework that can identify the redistributive contribution of the fiscal system without inheriting the limitations of either approach in isolation.

A growing body of work has attempted to bridge this gap through fiscal incidence analysis. Bhalla, Bhasin, and Virmani (2022)[Bhalla et al., 2022], in their IMF working paper, demonstrated that official poverty and inequality measures tend to overstate deprivation by ignoring the real economic value of government support delivered in kind. Accounting for food subsidies alone, their analysis showed a sharp reduction in measured inequality, with the consumption Gini falling to 0.294.

The most comprehensive application of this logic to the Indian fiscal system is the Commitment to Equity (CEQ) analysis conducted by Kundu and Cabrera (2022)[Kundu and Cabrera, 2022], which applied the CEQ framework - developed by Lustig (2018)[Lustig, 2018] and implemented across over 50 countries - to Indian data. Using NSS 68th Round (2011-12) consumption microdata, supplemented by the IHDS and NSS employment surveys, they traced the incidence of direct taxes, indirect taxes, subsidies, direct transfers, and public spending on education and health across the distribution. The Gini coefficient fell from 0.367 (Market Income plus Pensions) to 0.311 (Final Income), a compression of approximately 15.3 per cent. PDS food subsidies and public elementary education emerged as the two largest individual contributors to inequality reduction, with MGN-REGA and mid-day meals exhibiting strongly pro-poor concentration curves.

Taken together, Bhalla, Bhasin, and Virmani (2022), Kundu and Cabrera (2022), and the present study point in a common direction: India's fiscal system produces a measurable compression of market inequality, and inequality metrics that do not account for this compression may offer an incomplete picture of the distribution of economic resources available to households.

2.1 Why does our Gini diverge from the WIL Estimates?

A central task of this study is to explain why our estimated post-transfer Gini of about 0.262 sits far below the levels which are often close to 0.60 as reported by the World Inequality Lab. The gap does not arise from statistical noise or inconsistent data handling. It reflects a deeper difference in what is being measured and, more importantly, in how the role of the state is treated.

The World Inequality Lab's focus is on the pre-tax and pre-redistribution national income. This metric is designed to capture market outcomes like wages, profits, rents, and returns to capital before government intervention takes place. By construction, it asks how economic production and market power are distributed. In an economy where capital ownership and high-end earnings are highly concentrated, inequality measured at this stage will necessarily appear extreme. A high Gini in this framework is not an anomaly; it is the expected result.

This study, by contrast, is concerned with living standards rather than market rewards. The object of measurement is post-fiscal intervention disposable income, the resources households actually command after the state has acted. Market income is therefore aug-

mented by the monetised value of welfare transfers, capturing what families can consume, save, or invest once public support is taken into account. The shift is conceptual as much as statistical: from inequality of production to inequality of lived outcomes.

That distinction matters because much of India's redistribution operates through in-kind support that standard income metrics struggle to see. As noted in the work 'Pandemic, Poverty, and Inequality: Evidence from India', estimates based only on market income or raw consumption data tend to overstate deprivation when subsidies are excluded. This study explicitly prices the full welfare stack and adds it to household resources. Doing so raises the effective income floor of the bottom decile by nearly one-fifth, producing a compression in inequality that pre-tax measures are structurally blind to.

Differences also persist at the top of the distribution. While both approaches correct for the "missing rich" using Pareto-based techniques, the underlying definitions diverge. The DINA framework allocates all national income, including undistributed corporate profits and unrealised gains, to households at the top, offering a theoretical upper bound on concentration. Our approach relies on realised, taxable incomes drawn from ITR data, combined with survey evidence. The result is a closer approximation of disposable cash flows at the top relative to welfare-augmented incomes at the bottom.

Seen this way, the contrast between a Gini near 0.60 and one near 0.262 is not a contradiction. It captures the redistributive work performed by India's fiscal system, bridging a highly unequal market structure and a far more compressed pattern of final consumption.

a.) Exclusive Income Components incorporated by the World Inequality Lab

1. Undistributed Corporate Profits (Retained Earnings)

This component is the single largest driver of the difference at the top, representing the profit made by corporations that is not paid out as dividends to shareholders. For example, if a billionaire owns 100 per cent of a company that earns ₹1,000 Crores in profit, but the company only pays him ₹10 Crores in dividends, his "Tax Return Income" is only ₹10 Crores. However, his "National Income" share is effectively ₹1,000 Crores because he owns the company that holds that cash. Thus, their Top 10% income is artificially inflated by corporate wealth that households cannot spend today, pushing the Gini up.

2. Imputed Rent for Owner-Occupied Housing

Imputed rent is the estimated rental value of a home owned by the occupant. In National Accounts, living in your own house is treated as an economic service you provide to yourself. If you live in a house that would rent for ₹50,000/month, WIL treats that ₹50,000 as "Capital Income" you earned, even though no cash changed hands. This increases the income of the asset-owning class (middle and top) relative to the poor who rent, further widening the gap.

3. Tax-Exempt Investment Income

This component represents the interest, dividends, and capital gains earned in tax-sheltered accounts (like PPF, EPF, or insurance funds). Investment returns accumulating inside pension funds or tax-free bonds are real economic gains that the income tax returns data chooses to leave out. WIL imputes these flows back to the asset holders.

4. Pre-Tax Social Contributions

Pre-Tax Social Contributions are the payments made by employers for social security or pension schemes (for example, the employer's contribution to the Provident Fund).

2.2 A Cross-Country Analysis of the Divergence Between Income-Based and Consumption-Based Gini Estimates

Every country shows some gap between income inequality and consumption inequality. Richer households save more, poorer households spend more of what they earn, and the two curves never fully overlap. What makes India unusual is not the existence of this gap, but how wide it has become. Looking at other major economies side by side makes the reasons clearer.

Table 1: Global Divergence: Consumption vs. Income Gini Coefficients

Country	Consumption/ Disposable Income Inequality	Income-Based Inequality	Structural Insight
India	0.25	0.61	Extreme Divergence: Official stats measure <i>Consumption</i> , masking high capital accumulation. The 35-point gap reflects the "Savings Wedge."
South Africa	0.63	0.635	Structural Trap: Inequality permeates both earnings and survival consumption equally.
China	0.36	0.56	Moderate Gap: High savings rates exist, but a higher consumption floor moderates divergence.
USA	0.41 (Meyer & Sullivan)	0.59	Fiscal Wedge: Gap between Pre-Tax and Consumption inequality reflects redistributive impact of the tax system.
Germany	0.294	0.48	The Welfare State: High market inequality (0.49) crushed to 0.294 via massive redistribution.

Sources: World Bank Poverty and Inequality Platform (2023); World Inequality Database (2023); OECD (2024)

a.) Why India Looks So Different from Everyone Else

In India, the top end of the income distribution behaves very differently from the rest of the population. High-income households save aggressively (giving rise to the “Savings Wedge”), often putting money into assets that do not show up in everyday spending which spans through investments in land, housing, gold, long-term equity. This wealth accumulation barely touches consumption surveys. At the same time, lower-income households spend almost everything they earn, and often more than that once public support and informal credit are counted. The result is a sharp split between what people earn and what they actually consume.

How India measures inequality also deepens this divide. Official statistics rely heavily on consumption surveys, which do a good job of tracking mass living standards but rarely capture the lifestyles of the very rich. Big-ticket spending simply does not get sampled often enough. On top of that, much of India’s redistribution comes through goods and services rather than cash (for example, food rations, subsidised housing, free healthcare etc.). These supports directly raise consumption but leave little trace in income data. Put together, these features make consumption inequality look unusually low even as income inequality appears very high.

b.) China: High Savings, But Less Disconnect

China also saves a lot, but the gap between income and consumption inequality is far narrower. Public provision of housing, health, and local services reduces the extent to which private income differences translate into daily living standards. Survey coverage across urban households is also more even. High savings at the top exist, but they do not create the same break between earning and spending that appears in India.

c.) United States: Where Income and Consumption Move Together

In the United States, income inequality is high, yet consumption inequality is not dramatically lower. Middle-class households save through pensions and retirement accounts, while lower-income households use credit to smooth spending. Just as important, the data systems talk to each other. Tax records and household surveys are integrated, so the top of the distribution does not disappear from the numbers. The result is a relatively tight link between income and consumption measures.

d.) Germany: State Support Driving Change

Germany exemplifies how aggressive fiscal intervention can decouple market earnings from the standard of living. Despite a high Market Income Gini of 0.48 driven by a polarized labor market and a large demographic of pensioners with zero market wages, the state acts as a massive equalizer. Through a rigorously progressive tax system funding universal benefits like healthcare and Kindergeld (child benefits), Germany compresses this inequality by nearly 40%, resulting in a final Disposable Income Gini of 0.294. This massive divergence highlights that a nation’s final inequality metric is not defined by its market forces alone, but by the depth and efficiency of its social contract.

e.) South Africa: Inequality That Shows Up Everywhere

South Africa represents the starkest case of persistent inequality. Income inequality is extreme, and consumption inequality remains high as well. Redistribution has not been potent enough to materially narrow living-standard gaps, and survey instruments capture income directly. There is no hidden wedge between earning and spending, so both measures point in the same direction.

3. Methodology

3.1 Construction of the Income Distribution

a.) Distributional National Accounts (DINA) Framework

The empirical approach adopted in this study is conceptually aligned with the Distributional National Accounts (DINA) Guidelines 2025 [World Inequality Database, 2025a], developed by the World Inequality Lab and implemented through the World Inequality Database.

Traditional national accounts describe aggregate income but provide no information on how that income is shared across households or individuals. Conversely, household surveys provide distributional detail but often fail to capture high-income groups and typically do not reconcile with national income totals. The DINA framework bridges this divide by integrating macroeconomic accounts with micro-level distributional data, thereby constructing a distributional household income model. To do so, the DINA framework makes use of the “Generalised Pareto Interpolation” technique which shall act as the inspiration for our model.

Pareto interpolation is the mathematical bridge used to reconstruct the full, continuous income distribution from these fragmented data points. It is the empirical observation that income at the top of the distribution follows a “power law.” This means that as one moves higher up the income ladder, the number of people earning that income decreases at a predictable, non-linear rate.

The effort to adjust income distributions for welfare transfers in our paper represents an extension of this logic, moving from market income distributions toward a more comprehensive measure of economic resources available to households.

b.) Integrating Periodic Labour Force Survey Data and Income Tax Return Statistics

Accurate measurement of income inequality in developing economies presents a persistent methodological challenge. Household surveys capture the majority of the population but systematically underreport high incomes, while tax records accurately capture top incomes but exclude large segments of low-income and informal households. Relying on either source in isolation leads to biased inequality estimates.

To build a representative distribution of the annual household income, we employed a “Hybrid-Data Methodology” by combining information from the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) and Income Tax Return (ITR) statistics (AY 2023-24):

The Bottom 90% (Periodic Labour Force Survey): We derived the income distribution for the lower and middle strata from PLFS earnings microdata [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2024b]. Given that survey data often suffers from “right truncation bias” at the upper end, this dataset was utilised exclusively to model households earning below the 90th percentile of the modelled household income distribution.

Note: Truncation Bias manifests itself when data points are partially or completely outside a specific range, which ultimately leads to a skewed estimation of the population parameters.

The Top 10% (Income Tax Returns): To capture the “heavy tail” of high earners accurately, we utilised administrative tax return data [Income Tax Department, 2023]¹. This corrects for the under-reporting of income typically observed in voluntary surveys among the wealthy and thus tends to negate the truncation bias.

Note: The income measure adopted from the ITR database is Gross Total Income, which aggregates income across all heads (salary, house property, business/profession, capital gains, and other sources) before deductions under Chapter VI-A, thereby capturing the broadest available measure of realised market income at the individual level.

Our model actively uses the Decile System of 10-point distribution to distribute the Indian household population into 10 equal parts, with each decile earning a certain amount of money annually.

The regime threshold x_m is set at the 90th percentile of the modelled log-normal household income distribution, ensuring that the Pareto regime covers exactly the top 10 per cent of households. For FY 2024-25, this yields $x_m \approx ₹6.90$ Lakhs, which means that 90% of Indian households earn below this threshold. This value also serves as an approximate boundary between households that are net beneficiaries of the welfare architecture and those that transition into net fiscal contributors, though the correspondence between the statistical percentile and the policy-relevant welfare graduation boundary is approximate rather than exact.

1

The Pareto tail parameter (α) for the contemporary period is estimated from Income Tax Return statistics for Assessment Year 2023-24 (corresponding to income earned in FY 2022-23), published by the Central Board of Direct Taxes (CBDT) as Version 1.0 of the ITR Statistics release. As of the date of this study, AY 2023-24 represents the most recent assessment year for which CBDT has released tabulated income distribution data with the bracket-wise breakdowns required for Pareto interpolation. While ITR filings for AY 2024-25 (income earned in FY 2023-24) were completed by July 2024, with approximately 7.28 crore returns filed, the corresponding statistical tabulations have not yet been published by CBDT. The individual-level α is a slow-moving parameter, having shifted from approximately 1.414 to 1.536 to 1.62 over the decade spanning AY 2015-16 to AY 2023-24; a one-year lag in the ITR vintage is therefore unlikely to alter the household-level α by a magnitude that would materially affect the final Gini estimate.

c.) Individual-to-Household Income Aggregation

Both primary data sources, PLFS earnings microdata and ITR filing statistics, report income at the individual level. Since the unit of analysis in this study is the household, a systematic aggregation is required to convert person-level earnings into household-level market income. This conversion is a modelling assumption required to reconcile person-level labour-income data with household-level inequality measurement.

Derivation of the Earner-Pooling Multiplier. The baseline multiplier is set at 1.92 workers per household, derived from the interaction of three demographic parameters:

Table 2: Derivation of the Earner-Pooling Multiplier

Parameter	Value	Source
Average Household Size	4.4 members	NFHS-5 (2019–21) [International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF, 2022]
Share of Population Aged 15+	75%	UN Population Fund [United Nations Population Fund, 2025]
Worker Population Ratio (15+, Usual Status)	58.2%	PLFS 2023-24 Annual Report [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2024a]
Adults (15+) per Household	3.3	$= 4.4 \times 0.75$
Workers per Household	1.92	$= 3.3 \times 0.582$

Since not all workers are equivalent to stable income earners due to some being unpaid family helpers, irregular contributors, or low-intensity participants in the labour force, this figure is treated as a *calibration anchor* rather than a direct observed count of household earners. Accordingly, the model adopts 1.92 as the baseline householding parameter.

The earner-pooling multiplier is more operative at the lower end of the income distribution, where households are more likely to depend on multiple informal contributors to meet basic consumption needs, than at the top, where income tends to be concentrated in a single primary earner. This is consistent with household survey evidence indicating a higher prevalence of multi-earner structures among lower-income households [People Research on India’s Consumer Economy (PRICE), 2016]. Accordingly, the multiplier is applied to calibrate the Log-Normal regime (Deciles 1–9), while Decile 10 relies directly on ITR-reported individual income with minimal adjustment.

Regime-Specific Application. The multiplier operates differently across the two regimes of the income distribution:

For the *Bottom 90%* (Deciles 1–9), individual PLFS earnings were scaled by the baseline multiplier to obtain household-level market income. The log-normal parameters ($\mu = 12.74$, $\sigma = 0.55$) were then calibrated to this imputed household income distribution.

For the *Top 10%* (Decile 10), the individual-to-household adjustment is minimal. At higher income levels, household income is often dominated by a principal earner or principal income source (business proprietors, senior professionals, and capital-income recipi-

ents) making ITR-reported individual income a close approximation of household income. The Pareto parameters ($\alpha = 2.16$, $x_m = ₹6.90$ lakhs) were calibrated to the gross total income distribution reported in ITR statistics, with x_m set at the 90th percentile of the log-normal household income distribution.²

d.) Statistical Modelling of Income Distribution

The construction of the composite income distribution relies on a Two-Regime Parametric Model. This approach acknowledges that the income generation dynamics for the majority of the population (wage earners/small proprietors) differ fundamentally from those of the economic elite (capital owners/high-salaried professionals). Consequently, the population P was segmented at the 90th Percentile (P_{90}), with distinct probability density functions (PDFs) applied to each segment.

The Log-Normal Regime (Bottom 90%)

The income distribution for the Low-to-Middle Income Group was modelled using a Log-Normal Distribution, defined by the parameters $\mu = 12.74$ and $\sigma = 0.55$:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{x \sigma \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad x > 0 \quad (1)$$

In labour economics, the Log-Normal distribution is the standard prior for modelling earned income. This is based on ‘‘Gibrat’s Law of Proportionate Effect’’, which reflects multiplicative labour processes, hours worked, skill premia, sectoral constraints, producing a compressed but right-skewed wage profile.

Note: A right-skewed distribution indicates that the mass of the population is concentrated at low-to-moderate wage levels, while the mean is pulled upward by a long tail of high earners.

Parameter Interpretation:

Scale Parameter ($\mu = 12.74$): This represents the mean of the natural logarithm of income. This value acts as the ‘‘anchor’’ of the distribution, representing the typical central tendency of a household in the ‘‘Aspiring India’’ cohort (approx. ₹27,800 per month).

Note: The Economic Survey 2024–25 (Table 12.1, p. 378)[Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2025] reports average monthly earnings by employment category from PLFS 2023–24[Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2024a]: self-employed ₹13,279 (58.4% of workers), regular salaried ₹20,702 (21.7%), and casual labour ₹12,750 (19.8%), yielding an employment-weighted individual mean of approximately ₹14,785 per month. Annualised household earnings: ₹14,785 \times 1.92 \times 12 \approx ₹3,41,000; $\mu = \ln(341,000) \approx 12.74$.

²The regime threshold x_m is derived endogenously from the log-normal distribution as $x_m = \exp(\mu + \sigma \times z_{0.9})$, where $z_{0.9} \approx 1.2816$ is the 90th percentile of the standard normal distribution. For FY 2024–25, this yields $x_m = \exp(12.74 + 0.55 \times 1.2816) \approx ₹6,90,000$. This ensures that the Pareto regime covers exactly the top 10 per cent of the modelled household population, so that Decile 10 is structurally identical to the top decile by construction.

Shape Parameter ($\sigma = 0.55$): This represents the standard deviation of log-income, serving as a proxy for inequality within the poor and middle class. It indicates a relatively compressed distribution compared to the top tail, reflecting structural wage compression in the informal sector, where earnings variance is limited by subsistence constraints.

Note: The shape parameter $\sigma = 0.55$ implies a P90/P50 ratio of approximately 2.0, indicating that the 90th percentile household earns roughly twice the median. This is consistent with the well-documented divergence between income and consumption inequality in India, where income dispersion exceeds consumption dispersion due to rising savings rates across income levels.

The Pareto Regime (Top 10%)

The upper tail of the distribution ($P > 90$) was modelled using the Classical Pareto (Type I) Distribution, governed by the Tail Index $\alpha = 2.16$ and the Scale Parameter $x_m = ₹6.90$ lakhs:

$$f(x) = \frac{\alpha x_m^\alpha}{x^{\alpha+1}}, \quad x \geq x_m \quad (2)$$

In labour economics, the distribution of top incomes is widely observed to follow a Power Law, a statistical relationship in which the probability of earning above a given threshold declines not exponentially, as in a Log-Normal, but as a fixed power of that threshold. This produces a “fat tail” i.e. a slowly decaying population of very high earners that persists far beyond what a bell-curve framework would predict. The mechanism works on the assumption that the top incomes are generated not by additive labour processes but by multiplicative ones: asset appreciation, scalable business returns, equity compensation, and compounding capital gains.

Parameter Interpretation

The Regime Cutoff ($x_m = 6.90$ lakhs): This serves as the strict lower bound for the Pareto tail. It is derived endogenously as the 90th percentile of the log-normal household income distribution, ensuring that the Pareto regime covers exactly the top 10 per cent of the modelled population. The cutoff x_m therefore functions simultaneously as a statistical stitching point between the two distributional regimes and as an approximate boundary between net welfare beneficiaries and net fiscal contributors.

The Pareto Alpha ($\alpha = 2.16$): This is the Tail Index or “Inequality Parameter.” It dictates the “fatness” of the tail, specifically, the probability that an individual has an income higher than x .³

³The household-level Pareto α is derived from Income Tax Return statistics in two steps. First, the individual-level α is estimated as the local inter-bracket Pareto exponent between the ₹25 lakh and ₹50 lakh income brackets of the ITR distribution:

$$\alpha_{indiv} = \frac{\ln(N_{\geq 25L} \div N_{\geq 50L})}{\ln(50L \div 25L)}$$

where $N_{\geq x}$ denotes the number of tax returns with Gross Total Income at or above threshold x . This range is selected because it is the segment of the upper tail where the power-law relationship is most stable: below ₹25 lakhs, the estimate is inflated by the log-normal/Pareto transition zone, while above ₹50 lakhs,

3.2 Household Income Distribution Table

Table 3 presents the decile-wise distribution of annual household market income, derived from the two-regime parametric model described above.

Table 3: Decile-wise Household Income Distribution (Pre-Fiscal)

Decile	Mean Annual Income (₹)	Mean Monthly Income (₹)	Income Share (%)
1	1,32,973	11,081	3.07
2	1,92,497	16,041	4.44
3	2,35,329	19,611	5.43
4	2,76,053	23,004	6.37
5	3,18,542	26,545	7.35
6	3,65,897	30,491	8.45
7	4,22,311	35,193	9.75
8	4,95,727	41,311	11.44
9	6,07,408	50,617	14.02
10	12,84,828	1,07,069	29.66
Total	43,31,565		100.00

Figure 1 demonstrates the “Hockey Stick Curve” Nature of the Distribution of Household Income.

the local exponent collapses below 1.0 as extreme-tail capital income dynamics dominate. This approach is consistent with the Generalised Pareto Interpolation technique employed in the DINA framework, which estimates local Pareto coefficients between adjacent thresholds of tabulated tax data rather than fitting a single global exponent. For AY 2023-24, this yields $\alpha_{indiv} \approx 1.62$. Second, the individual-level α is converted to a household-level parameter by applying a compression multiplier of approximately $4/3$ (≈ 1.33), reflecting the empirical regularity that household income distributions exhibit thinner tails than individual distributions due to the pooling of earnings across household members. This directional assumption is consistent with Gaillard, Hellwig, Wangner, and Werquin (2023)[Gaillard et al., 2023], who document that household-level Pareto coefficients estimated from survey data are systematically higher than individual-level estimates derived from administrative tax records. The resulting household $\alpha \approx 1.62 \times 4/3 \approx 2.16$. The $4/3$ multiplier is a calibration assumption rather than an econometrically estimated parameter; its sensitivity is documented in the limitations section.

Figure 1: Pre-Transfer Market Income Distribution

The Hockey-Stick Curve: The curve shows a gradual, linear increase from the bottom to the middle class (D1 to D9), followed by a sharp exponential spike at the top decile (D10). This visual shape, often referred to as the “Hockey Stick” curve, is characteristic of unequal income distributions where the top tail breaks away from the rest of the population.

3.3 Valuation of Welfare Transfers

Welfare transfers are seldom accounted for in inequality indices. The Indian government provides a multitude of social safety nets to the lower and middle-income groups of society, which significantly expands their lump-sum disposable income.

Note: Transfers are valued conservatively using realised expenditures and coverage figures rather than headline entitlements. Capital-intensive schemes are annualised over reasonable asset lifetimes, and insurance schemes are valued using expected claims rather than maximum coverage limits. All scheme outlays are annualised where necessary and averaged across the welfare-eligible household base (27 crore households) to produce a comparable per-household value. India’s total household base is estimated at approximately 30 crore (296 million in 2025), based on National Statistical Office estimates as compiled by Helgi Library (2025)[Helgi Library, 2025]. The welfare-eligible population (bottom 90%) accordingly comprises approximately 27 crore households.

Below is an elaborate description of the methodology employed to calculate the welfare benefits accruing from each scheme.

1. Public Distribution System (Under National Food Security Act)

Under NFSA, 81.35 crore individuals are covered. With a household size of 4, this corresponds to approximately 20.34 crore households.

Total annual foodgrain allocation for 2025–26[Press Information Bureau, 2024] is:

Commodity	Allocation (lakh tonnes)
Rice	406.48
Wheat	193.32
Nutri-cereals	8.37
Total	608.17

To stay conservative and avoid overestimating, we use a single conservative market benchmark of rice: ₹29/kg (Bharat Rice's MRP), since rice is the most widely distributed food grain. The PDS issue price has been reduced to ₹0/kg [DD News, 2025]).

Thus, the effective market value of the PDS subsidy is ₹29 – ₹0 = ₹29/kg of food grain. Thus, the final annual market value of the PDS subsidised grains transfer will be approximately ₹1.76 lakh crores divided by the total number of households covered (20.34).

Final Transfer = ₹8,671/household/year

2. PM-Kisan Samman Nidhi

PM-Kisan provides ₹6,000 annually to each eligible farmer household [Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, 2024]. The latest installment confirms 9 crore beneficiaries. We shall calculate the broad income support reaching rural households while being spread across the full low-income base.

Final Transfer = ₹2,000/household/year.

3. Ayushman Bharat – Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana

PMJAY, a government-funded health assurance scheme, provides up to ₹5 lakh/household/year for secondary and tertiary care hospitalisation to about 12 crore poor and vulnerable families, with the premium jointly funded by the Central and State governments in a 60:40 ratio.

In the fiscal year 2024–25 (April–October), 2.02 crore insurance claims amounting to ₹28,732 crores were settled [Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2024]. To avoid double-counting with state-level welfare transfers, we isolate the Central Government's share of the claims value by applying the statutory 60:40 funding ratio, yielding a central contribution of ₹17,239 crores. This amount is distributed over our base of 27 crore welfare-eligible households.

Final Transfer = ₹638/household/year

4. Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY)

PMAY provides affordable housing to the eligible urban and rural poor by providing an interest subsidy of up to ₹1.8 lakhs/unit (under PMAY-U 2.0) and one-time capital assistance of ₹1.20 lakh (plain areas) to ₹1.30 lakh (hilly areas) under PMAY-G and financial assistance of up to ₹2.50 lakh per housing unit is provided to eligible urban poor and middle-class families under PMAY-Urban (2.0). However, since it is a capital transfer rather than a recurring flow of income, we have to annualise this transfer over

the service life of the dwelling (conservatively taken as ~ 20 years) while also weighting it by coverage probability within the welfare-eligible population [Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2025] [DD News, 2024].

As of late 2025, over 1.22 crore houses have been sanctioned under PMAY-Urban (including PMAY-U 2.0), while over 4.12 crore houses have been allocated/sanctioned under PMAY-Gramin.

We first have to figure out the annualised central benefit that each beneficiary household is receiving. Under PMAY-G, the total unit assistance of ₹1.20 lakh is shared between the Centre and State governments in a 60:40 ratio, with the Central share being ₹72,000 per house. Annualised over 20 years, this yields ₹3,600 per rural beneficiary household. Under PMAY(U)-2.0, the Central assistance of ₹2.50 lakh per unit, annualised over 20 years, yields ₹12,500 per urban beneficiary household. Thus, the Total Central Welfare Value Generated will be:

Component	Total Unit Assistance	Central Share	Annualised ($\div 20$ yrs)	Beneficiary HHs (Cr)	Total Value (Crore)
PMAY-G (Plain)	₹1,20,000	60% = ₹72,000	₹3,600	4.12	₹14,832
PMAY-U 2.0	₹2,50,000	100% = ₹2,50,000	₹12,500	1.22	₹15,250
Total					₹30,082

Final Transfer = ₹1,114/household/year.

5. PM Ujjwala Yojana

Under the PM Ujjwala Yojana [Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas, 2025], the government provides cash assistance of up to ₹1600 per household, in addition to a free hot plate and a targeted subsidy of ₹300 (per cylinder) provided for up to 9–12 annual refills. Till now, approximately 10.3 crore households have been covered, with an addition of 25 lakh more households in the year 2025.

For calculation purposes, we take:

Cash Assistance = ₹1375 (Average Value)

No. of refills = 9 refills/household

Price of Hot Plate (Stove) = ₹1,500

Given the above values, to calculate our welfare transfer culminating from this scheme, we will make use of the recurring value of subsidy by taking into account the 10.3 crore existing beneficiaries in addition to the 25 lakh newly added households to give the picture of the real amount of money transferred by the government to the beneficiaries. We shall include the first-time benefits (like initial financial support of ₹1375 to cover security deposit, installation charges etc. and free hot plate) for the new connections of 2025.

Component	Target HHs	Unit Benefit (Annual)	Total Value (Crore)
Recurring Subsidy	10.55 Cr (All Users)	₹300 × 9 = ₹2,700	₹28,485 Cr
New Connection Capital	25 Lakh (New Users)	₹1,375 + ₹1,500 Stove	₹719 Cr

Final Transfer= ₹1081/household/year.

6. Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM)

The Union Budget 2024–25 allocated ₹70,163 crore to the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM)[PRS Legislative Research, 2024], a Centrally Sponsored Scheme. However, the actual expenditure for FY 2024–25 was ₹22,615 crore, reflecting implementation constraints and slower-than-anticipated state-level fund absorption[PRS Legislative Research, 2026a]. We adopt the Actuals (2024-25) as the operative central outlay. Since the state contribution is captured under State-Level Welfare Transfers, only the Central share is accounted for here.

Final Transfer = ₹838/household/year.

7. Integrated Child Development Services

The Integrated Child Development Services, now restructured as Saksham Anganwadi and POSHAN 2.0, is an umbrella scheme targeting health, nutrition and development of children under the age of 6 years, pregnant women and lactating mothers. It offers supplementary nutrition, immunisation, health check-ups, etc.

The Budget Estimate for FY 2024–25 was ₹21,200 crore, while the actual expenditure stood at ₹21,014 crore[PRS Legislative Research, 2026b]. Consistent with our methodology of valuing transfers at realised fiscal outlays, we adopt the Actuals (2024-25) value as the operative central outlay.

Final Transfer = ₹779/household/year.

8. PM Poshan Scheme

PM POSHAN (or the Midday-Meal scheme) provides free, cooked meals to students in Classes I–VIII in government and aided schools to deliver essential nutrition to almost 11 crore children[Press Information Bureau, 2025a]. The following table provides us with the cost per meal and the annual monetary value of the meals, assuming that there are 200 school-working days and there is one school-going child per household.

Category	Cost per Meal (2025)	Annual Monetary Value
Primary (Class 1–5) & Balvatika	₹12.13	₹2,426
Upper Primary (Class 6–8)	₹17.62	₹3,524

Final Transfer= ₹2,975 per child per year (Each household is assumed to contain one eligible child)

9. Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM)

The Swachh Bharat Mission[PM India, 2025], launched in 2014, is a country-wide campaign aimed at achieving a clean India by eliminating open defecation and improving solid waste management. The scheme is funded in a 60:40 ratio between the Centre and States. As per the Government’s reply in Lok Sabha[Press Information Bureau, 2025b], the Central Government released ₹3,622 crore under SBM-Gramin and ₹1,893 crore under SBM-Urban in FY 2024–25, totalling ₹5,515 crore.

Final Transfer = ₹204/household/year.

10. National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM)

The Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana – NRLM aims to reduce rural poverty by organising rural poor women into SHGs[Ministry of Rural Development, 2025]. In 2025, a major release of ₹1,625 Cr was recently announced for capital support to 4.07 Lakh SHGs, along with an interest subvention of over ₹3,300 crores, which has been provided to keep the effective interest rate for SHG loans at 7% or lower, taking the total outlay to ₹4,925 crore. However, the NRLM benefits reach approximately 9 crore households, and it is skewed towards poorer and lower-middle households. But, to evenly distribute this whole pie amongst all the beneficiary households, we shall take the average amount receiving each beneficiary household.

Final Transfer= ₹183/household/year.

11. Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGN-REGA)

MGNREGA Scheme[Department of Rural Development, Government of India, nd] provides a legal guarantee of 100 days of paid, unskilled manual work. Since, the per day wage provided to the labourers varies state-to-state, we take the average per day wage value of ₹295. As per the Ministry of Rural Development Dashboard for the fiscal year of 2025-26, the person-days generated were 184.68 crore and the number of active workers was 12.17 crore. For the calculation of the effective welfare benefit transfer, we calculated the total wage outlay by multiplying the total number of person days generated with the per day wage amount, which yielded us the value of Rs. 54480 crores. Assuming that each household bears only one MGNREGA worker, we get

Final Transfer= ₹4,476/household/year

12. State-Level Welfare Transfers

The estimation relies on the latest fiscal data regarding “Social Welfare Spending” and “Power Sector Subsidy Support” from India’s states. The baseline is derived from the CRISIL Ratings 2025 report on the Top 18 States, extrapolated to a national (All-India) estimate.

Primary Data Source: CRISIL Ratings (June 2025) – “State of State Finances: The Rise of the Welfare State.” [CRISIL Ratings, 2025]

Secondary Validation: RBI State Finances Report (January 2025) – “Budget Estimates

and Social Expenditure Trends.” [Reserve Bank of India, 2024]

Baseline (Top 18 States): CRISIL reports aggregate social welfare spending for the top 18 states at ₹6.40 Lakh Crore. Since these states represent 90% of national GSDP, the remaining 10 states and Union Territories add approximately 10% to the fiscal pot ($6.4 \div 0.90 \approx 7.11$).

Non-Departmental Subsidies: RBI data indicates significant welfare flows (specifically “Zero-Bill” power and transport subsidies) are often booked under Energy/Transport Departments or PSU support, not Social Welfare. We estimate this “Hidden Welfare” conservatively at ₹0.39 Lakh Crore.

To derive the per-household impact, we distribute this aggregate “All-India” fiscal pot across the Target Population.

Table 4: Derivation of State-Level Welfare Vector (T_{State})

Variable	Value	Source / Calculation Logic
(A) Top 18 States Welfare Spend	₹6,40,000 Cr	CRISIL Ratings (2025): Aggregate Social Welfare Dept outlays for major states (accounting for $\approx 90\%$ GSDP).
(B) National Extrapolation	₹7,11,111 Cr	Adjustment: Extrapolated to All-India level ($(A) \div 0.90$) to cover remaining states/UTs.
(C) Off-Budget/Utility Adj.	₹38,889 Cr	RBI (2025): Estimate of implicit subsidies booked under Energy/Transport (e.g., free power/bus) rather than Welfare.
(D) Total Welfare Pot (W_{Total})	₹7,50,000 Cr	Aggregate State Fiscal Outlay ($(B) + (C)$)
(E) Target Population	27.0 Crore HH	User Estimate: Represents the Bottom 90% of India’s ≈ 30 Cr Households.
(F) Final Transfer Value (T_{State})	₹27,777	Per Household Transfer ($(D) \div (E)$)

Sources: CRISIL Ratings (June 2025) for Base Outlay; RBI State Finances (Jan 2025) for Utility Subsidies; NSSO for Household Composition.

Final Transfer = ₹27,777/household/year

13. Public Education Transfers (Imputed Value)

The Indian state also provides substantial “In-Kind Transfers” through the public education system. For a household, the provision of free schooling functions as Imputed Income as it represents the “Avoided Cost” of private tuition, freeing up disposable income for other consumption.

The valuation is anchored in the Comprehensive Modular Survey on Education-NSS 80th Round-2025 [National Sample Survey Office, MoSPI, 2025], which provides the most granular data on household social consumption. The survey reports that the average annual out-of-pocket expenditure per student in a Private Unaided Institution is ₹25,002. This serves as the “Market Price” of education. In contrast, the average expenditure for a student in a Government Institution (covering incidental costs like books/uniforms) is just ₹2,863.

The Net Savings Value:

$$\text{Savings} = \text{Cost}_{Private} - \text{Cost}_{Govt} = |22,139$$

To ensure conservative estimation, we do not assume 100% saturation. Instead, we apply a Participation Probability Weight (P_{agg}) of 56%. This figure is derived from the Comprehensive Modular Survey on Education-NSS 80th Round-2025.

$$T_{Edu} = \text{Net Saving (₹22,139)} \times P_{agg}(0.56) = \mathbf{₹12,397} \approx \mathbf{₹12,400}$$

Note: These figures refer to the percentage of students enrolled in government institutions at the primary and upper primary levels.

3.4 Final Welfare Transfer

Table 5 showcases the complete data related to the welfare schemes along with their respective valuations and the required eligibility conditions.

Table 5: Welfare Scheme Valuation Matrix (FY 2024–25)

No.	Welfare Scheme	Nature of Transfer	Annual Value per HH (₹)	Targeted Population	Eligibility Conditions
1	Public Distribution System (NFSA / Anna Yojana)	In-kind (Food Subsidy)	8,671	~81.4 Cr Individuals	Priority Households (PHH) & Antyodaya (AAY)
2	PM-Kisan Samman Nidhi	Cash Transfer	2,000	~9.0 Cr Farmers	Landholding farmers; Excludes tax payers / gov emp
3	Ayushman Bharat (PMJAY)	Health Insurance (Service)	638	~12 Cr Families	SECC 2011 Criteria, Occupational, Seniors (70+)
4	Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY)	Capital Transfer (Housing)	1,114	~5.4 Cr Houses	Houseless / Kuccha wall; EWS/LIG Income limits
5	PM Ujjwala Yojana	Fuel Subsidy + Access	1,081	~10.4 Cr Connections	Adult women (BPL, SC/ST); No existing connection

No.	Welfare Scheme	Nature of Transfer	Annual Value per HH (₹)	Targeted Population	Eligibility Conditions
6	Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM)	Public Service (Water)	838	~15 Cr Households	Universal coverage for rural households
7	ICDS (Anganwadi)	Nutrition & Health	779	~10 Cr Beneficiaries	Children (0–6y) & Pregnant / Lactating Mothers
8	PM POSHAN (Mid-Day Meal)	In-kind Nutrition	2,975	~11.8 Cr Children	Students in Gov & Aided Schools (Class I–VIII)
9	Swachh Bharat Mission	Sanitation Infra	204	Universal Access	HHs without toilets; Incentive for BPL/APL
10	NRLM	Credit Subsidy / Income Support	183	~10 Cr Women	Rural poor women (PIP); One per household
11	MGNREGA	Guaranteed Wage Support	4,476	~12 Cr Households	Unskilled Manual Labourer from Rural Household
12	State-Level Welfare Transfers	Support through state-level schemes	27,777	-	State-Specific Coverage
13	Public Education Transfers	Govt-funded education	12,400	~10 Cr Households	Children aged 6–14 under the RTE Act/Neighborhood Proximity/Income/Caste

All welfare benefits received by the eligible households across schemes are converted into monetary equivalents and aggregated into a single consolidated transfer T_i . The model assumes a “Inverse-MPCE Targeting” approach within the Deciles 1-9, where the transfer is applied in proportion to the MPCE Valuation.

3.5 Deduction of Direct Personal Taxes (D_{tax})

To transition from Gross Lived Income to Disposable Lived Income, the analysis must incorporate the direct tax liabilities borne by households at the upper end of the distribution. Gross lived income aggregates market earnings with the monetised value of welfare transfers, capturing the full inflow of economic resources available to a household. Disposable lived income extends this measure by deducting statutory tax obligations, thereby arriving at the net command over resources that households actually retain. Without this adjustment, the fiscal incidence framework remains incomplete, accounting for the benefit side of state intervention while omitting the contribution side.

The bottom 90 percent of households are, on net, beneficiaries of the fiscal system once transfers are incorporated into their income. The top decile, by contrast, functions as the principal net contributor to the redistributive architecture.

For estimating tax liability (D_{Tax}), this study adopts the New Tax Regime under Section 115BAC as amended by the Finance Act, 2024, applicable for Assessment Year 2025–26 [Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2024]

The representative household of Decile 10 has an average market income of ₹12,84,828. The tax liability is calculated using the progressive marginal tax slabs (the “Waterfall Method”) after applying the standard deduction.

Table 6: Statutory Tax Deduction (D_{Tax}): Waterfall Calculation (New Regime FY25)

A. Determination of Taxable Income			
Avg. Market Income (Decile 10)			12,84,828
Less: Standard Deduction (Budget 2024)			(-) 75,000
Net Taxable Income			12,09,828
B. Slab-wise Calculation (Waterfall)			
Income Slab	Tax Rate	Taxable Amount	Tax Due (₹)
0 – 3,00,000	Nil	3,00,000	0
3,00,001 – 7,00,000	5%	4,00,000	20,000
7,00,001 – 10,00,000	10%	3,00,000	30,000
10,00,001 – 12,00,000	15%	2,00,000	30,000
12,00,001 – 12,09,828	20%	9,828	1,966
		Base Tax Liability	81,966
		Add: Health & Education Cess (4%)	+ 3,279
		Total Tax Deduction (D_{Tax})	85,244

Note: Calculated under Section 115BAC (New Tax Regime) as per Finance Act 2024. Applied exclusively to Decile 10.

Thus, Final Tax Deduction for the top Decile (D10) = ₹85,244

Final Disposable Lived Income

Our Final Disposable Lived Income is defined as:

$$Y_i^{net} = \begin{cases} Y_i + T_{transfer} & \text{for } i \in \{1, \dots, 9\} \\ Y_i - D_{tax} & \text{for } i = 10 \end{cases}$$

where,

- Y_i^{net} : Annual Household Income(Post-Fiscal Intervention).
- Y_i : Annual Household Income (Pre-Fiscal Intervention).
- $T_{transfer}$: Targeted Welfare Transfer Benefit. Applies to Deciles 1–9.
- D_{tax} : Statutory Direct Tax Liability (₹85,244). Deducted exclusively from Decile 10 under the New Tax Regime (FY25).

3.6 Derivation Methodology of the Gini Coefficient

Our study employs a Static Fiscal Incidence Microsimulation to estimate the impact of government welfare transfers and direct personal taxes on household income inequality. The objective is to calculate the Post-Transfer Gini Coefficient by adjusting market income for state-provided cash and asset benefits while also adjusting for the tax that is scooped off the income of the top decile. The model distinguishes between “Market Income” (pre-intervention) and “Disposable Income” (post-intervention).

Note: Static fiscal incidence microsimulation is a modelling technique that analyses the immediate, “morning-after” distributional impacts of tax and benefit reforms on individuals or households without accounting for behavioural responses. By applying policy rules to representative, detailed survey data, it calculates the direct change in disposable income, allowing policymakers to assess the equity and revenue effects across different income groups.

The estimation protocol followed a rigorous four-stage theoretical process to ensure robustness of methodology.

I. Population Segmentation (Decile Construction)

The post-transfer income distribution was first organised by sorting all households in ascending order of their disposable income, from the poorest to the richest. This ordered population was then segmented into ten equal groups, or deciles, each representing exactly 10% of the total household population. This segmentation allows for a structured analysis of how income accumulates across different strata of society.

II. Geometric Integration (The Trapezoidal Rule)

Since the data is grouped into deciles rather than a continuous stream, we employed the “Trapezoidal Rule” to measure the area under the Lorenz Curve. The basis of this rule involves connecting the data points of each decile with straight lines to form trapezoids, after which the total area covered by these trapezoids is calculated.

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i)(Y_i + Y_{i-1})$$

where,

- P_i : The cumulative share of the population (always increments of 0.1 for deciles);
- Y_i : The cumulative share of Lived Income held by that decile.

III. Derivation of the Gini Coefficient

The final Gini coefficient is calculated as a ratio of areas. It measures the size of the “Inequality Gap,” the area between the theoretical Line of Equality and our observed Lorenz Curve.

A coefficient of 0 implies perfect equality (all the households are at a perfectly equal level with regard to annual income).

A coefficient of 1 implies perfect inequality (one household holds all the income).

3.7 Pre-Fiscal Intervention Income Gini Coefficient (G_{Pre})

To quantify the inherent inequality generated by the market economy prior to any state redistribution, we first calculate the Pre-Fiscal Gini Coefficient (G_{Market}). This metric isolates the distribution of “Market Income” (L_i), defined as the aggregate of wages, salaries, self-employment income, and returns on capital, excluding all government transfers and taxes.

Table 7 shows us the methodology of deriving the required variables for the calculation of the ‘Pre Fiscal Intervention Income Gini Coefficient’.

Table 7: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: Market Income (G_{Market})

Decile	Mean Market Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	1,32,973	3.07%	0.0307	0.0000	0.0307
2	1,92,497	4.44%	0.0751	0.0307	0.1058
3	2,35,329	5.43%	0.1295	0.0751	0.2046
4	2,76,053	6.37%	0.1932	0.1295	0.3227
5	3,18,542	7.35%	0.2667	0.1932	0.4599
6	3,65,897	8.45%	0.3512	0.2667	0.6179
7	4,22,311	9.75%	0.4487	0.3512	0.7999
8	4,95,727	11.44%	0.5632	0.4487	1.0119
9	6,07,408	14.02%	0.7034	0.5632	1.2665
10	12,84,828	29.66%	1.0000	0.7034	1.7034
TOTAL	43,31,565	100%		SUM (Σ):	6.5234

Substituting the area calculation from Step 3, the final computational formula used in this study is:

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 6.5234 = 1 - 0.6523 \quad (4)$$

$$\boxed{G \approx 0.348} \quad (5)$$

3.8 MPCE-Based Post Fiscal Intervention Gini Coefficient (G_{Post})

To achieve a precise estimate of fiscal incidence, this study moves beyond the assumption of uniform welfare distribution. A flat, equal allocation of transfers across all deciles would fail to reflect the reality that lower-income households are structurally more dependent on public provisioning than wealthier ones. Instead, we employ an inverse consumption weighting model based on Monthly Per Capita Expenditure (MPCE) data from the All India Household Consumption Expenditure Survey (HCES) 2022-23 [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, 2024].

The underlying logic is established in the understanding that a household's reliance on publicly provided goods and services is inversely proportional to its private purchasing power. Households at the bottom of the distribution depend disproportionately on PDS foodgrains, government schools, public health facilities, and subsidised cooking fuel, while households at the top substitute toward private alternatives. Distributing the welfare pool uniformly would therefore understate the concentration of benefits at the bottom and overstate it at the top.

To operationalise this, we assign a Need Weight (W_i) to each decile, defined as the inverse of its MPCE, normalised across the eligible population (Deciles 1 through 9):

$$W_i = \frac{1}{\text{MPCE}_i} \div \sum_{i=1}^9 \frac{1}{\text{MPCE}_i}$$

The consolidated welfare pool is then allocated in proportion to these weights ensuring that the decile with the lowest consumption floor (Decile 1, MPCE ₹1,783) receives the largest share of transfers (20.6%), with the share declining monotonically as household consumption rises.

In the model, Decile 10 is excluded from targeted transfers, reflecting the fact that the principal means-tested schemes in the welfare stack are not designed around upper-income or tax-paying households, and that utilisation of publicly targeted schemes is negligible at the top of the distribution. For the remaining schemes where eligibility is formally universal, such as MGNREGA and JJM, empirical utilisation among households above the 90th percentile is negligible, rendering the exclusion consistent with observed demand patterns.

Table 8 gives us the derivation of the progressive welfare shares.

Table 8: Derivation of Progressive Welfare Shares (Inverse MPCE Method)

Decile	Avg. MPCE (All India) ₹	Inverse Score (1 ÷ MPCE)	Share of Total Need Score (%)	Allocated Transfer Value (₹)
1	1,783	0.000561	20.64%	+ 1,17,308
2	2,408	0.000415	15.29%	+ 86,861
3	2,825	0.000354	13.03%	+ 74,039
4	3,216	0.000311	11.45%	+ 65,037
5	3,624	0.000276	10.16%	+ 57,715
6	4,080	0.000245	9.02%	+ 51,265
7	4,634	0.000216	7.94%	+ 45,136
8	5,370	0.000186	6.85%	+ 38,950
9	6,554	0.000153	5.62%	+ 31,913
10	10,849	<i>Excluded</i>	0.00%	0
TOTAL		0.002717	100.00%	₹5,68,224

Source: MPCE data from All India Household Consumption Expenditure Survey 2022-23. Welfare shares are calculated inversely to consumption for Deciles 1–9. Decile 10 is statutorily excluded from the welfare pool.

Table 9 shows the final consolidated fiscal impact on all the deciles by incorporating welfare transfers and income tax deductions.

Table 9: Consolidated Fiscal Impact: Market vs. Lived Income (FY 2024-25)

Decile	Pre-Intervention Market Income	Net Fiscal Intervention	Post-Intervention Lived Income	Net Change (%)
1	₹1,32,973	+ ₹1,17,308	₹2,50,281	+88.2%
2	₹1,92,497	+ ₹86,861	₹2,79,358	+45.1%
3	₹2,35,329	+ ₹74,039	₹3,09,368	+31.5%
4	₹2,76,053	+ ₹65,037	₹3,41,090	+23.6%
5	₹3,18,542	+ ₹57,715	₹3,76,257	+18.1%
6	₹3,65,897	+ ₹51,265	₹4,17,161	+14.0%
7	₹4,22,311	+ ₹45,136	₹4,67,447	+10.7%
8	₹4,95,727	+ ₹38,950	₹5,34,677	+7.9%
9	₹6,07,408	+ ₹31,913	₹6,39,321	+5.3%
10	₹12,84,828	– ₹85,244	₹11,99,583	–6.6%

Methodology Note: Welfare transfers are distributed based on Inverse MPCE Weighting (HCES 2022-23), targeting the bottom 90% progressively. Decile 10 is the sole net payer of Direct Taxes. This fiscal structure yields a final **Gini Coefficient of 0.262**.

Figure 2 shows the decile-wise impact of the fiscal intervention by the government.

Figure 2: Decile-wise Impact of Welfare Targeting

Having established the Lived Income for each decile, we now quantify the aggregate level of inequality in this new distribution. To do this, we construct the Lorenz Curve coordinates and derive the Gini coefficient using the Trapezoidal Rule.

Table 10: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: Final Targeted Model ($G_{Net} = 0.262$)

Decile	Mean Lived Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	2,50,281	5.20%	0.0520	0.0000	0.0520
2	2,79,358	5.80%	0.1100	0.0520	0.1620
3	3,09,368	6.43%	0.1743	0.1100	0.2843
4	3,41,090	7.08%	0.2451	0.1743	0.4194
5	3,76,257	7.82%	0.3233	0.2451	0.5684
6	4,17,161	8.66%	0.4099	0.3233	0.7332
7	4,67,447	9.71%	0.5070	0.4099	0.9169
8	5,34,677	11.11%	0.6181	0.5070	1.1250
9	6,39,321	13.28%	0.7508	0.6181	1.3689
10	11,99,583	24.92%	1.0000	0.7508	1.7508
TOTAL	48,14,544	100%		SUM (Σ):	7.3809

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \tag{6}$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 7.3809 = 1 - 0.7381 \tag{7}$$

$$G \approx 0.262 \tag{8}$$

3.9 Building of the Lorenz Curve

Our formulated Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix provides us with a standard to construct the Lorenz Curve. The Lorenz Curve plots the cumulative percentage of households (horizontal X-axis) against the cumulative percentage of total national income (vertical Y-axis) they possess. The resulting curve visualises the “income gap.” In a perfectly equal society, the Bottom $x\%$ would own exactly $x\%$ of the income, resulting in a straight Line of Equality (a 45-degree diagonal).

By measuring how far the post-intervention Lorenz Curve shifts inward compared to the pre-intervention curve, this metric provides a precise, standardised value for the redistributive efficiency of the welfare intervention.

Figure 3: Post-Welfare Transfer Disposable Income Lorenz Curve

4. Historical Benchmark: Estimating the Lived Income Gini for FY 2017-18

To evaluate whether India’s fiscal redistribution has strengthened or stagnated over time, we apply the identical methodological framework developed for FY 2024-25 to the fiscal year 2017-18. This year is chosen as the temporal anchor for three reasons: (i) it is the base year of the first Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS), providing robust earnings microdata; (ii) three major welfare schemes – PM-Kisan, Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY), and the Jal Jeevan Mission (JJM) – had not yet been launched, allowing us to measure their incremental impact; and (iii) it predates both the COVID-19 pandemic and the universalisation of free foodgrain distribution under PMGKAY, isolating the structural welfare architecture from emergency provisioning.

4.1 Calibration of the Income Distribution

The Pre-fiscal income distribution for FY 2017-18 is constructed using the same hybrid two-regime model: a Log-Normal distribution for the bottom 90% of households and a Pareto distribution for the top 10%.

Log-Normal Parameters (μ , σ)

The mean of the log-income distribution (μ) is derived from PLFS 2017-18 earnings data [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2019]. Weighted average monthly individual earnings across employment categories are computed using actual reported earnings for the July–September 2017 quarter - the first and most structurally representative quarter of the survey period - with casual labour earnings converted to a monthly equivalent on a 30-day basis:

Table 11: Weighted Individual Earnings, PLFS 2017-18

Category	Monthly Earnings (₹)	Employment Share	Contribution (₹)
Self-Employed	11,885	52.2%	6,204
Regular Salaried	15,845	22.8%	3,613
Casual Labour	7,290	24.9%	1,815
Weighted Average			11,632

Note: Casual labour daily earnings of ₹243 per day (PLFS 2017-18, July–September quarter, non-public works) are converted to a monthly equivalent by multiplying by 30 days, yielding ₹7,290 per month. Employment shares sum to 99.9% due to rounding of PLFS-reported category proportions.

The earner multiplier for 2017-18 is derived as follows:

Table 12: Derivation of the Earner-Pooling Multiplier (FY 2017-18)

Parameter	Value	Source
Average Household Size	4.5 members	NFHS-4 and NHFS-5 [International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF, 2022]
Share of Population Aged 15+	73%	MOSPI [National Statistical Office, 2022]
Worker Population Ratio (15+, Usual Status)	46.8%	PLFS 2017-18 Annual Report [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2019]
Adults (15+) per Household	3.29	$= 4.5 \times 0.73$
Workers per Household	1.54	$= 3.29 \times 0.468$

The standard deviation of log-incomes (σ) is held constant at 0.55, consistent with the FY 2024-25 estimation. The ratio of upper-middle to lower-income households has remained structurally stable across this period; the structural determinants of this spread (rural-urban wage gaps, education premiums, sectoral employment composition) evolved slowly relative to the seven-year comparison window.

Pareto Parameters (α , x_m)

The regime threshold x_m is set at the 90th percentile of the log-normal household income distribution, consistent with the methodology adopted for FY 2024-25. For FY 2017-18, $x_m = \exp(12.28 + 0.55 \times 1.2816) \approx ₹4,36,000$.⁴

The Pareto shape parameter (α) is set at 2.05 for FY 2017-18, derived by applying the household compression multiplier ($4/3 \approx 1.33$) to the individual-level α estimated from ITR statistics for AY 2018-19 [Central Board of Direct Taxes, 2019] – the assessment year governing income earned during FY 2017-18. The individual α is estimated as the local inter-bracket Pareto exponent between the ₹25 lakh and ₹50 lakh income brackets of the ITR distribution, yielding $\alpha_{indiv} \approx 1.536$. After applying the household compression multiplier, this yields an effective household $\alpha \approx 1.536 \times 4/3 \approx 2.05$.

⁴Income Tax Return statistics for AY 2018-19 report Gross Total Income (GTI), i.e. income across all heads before Chapter VI-A deductions. The Pareto distribution is accordingly calibrated to GTI, and the tax computation applies statutory deductions to arrive at taxable income before applying the relevant slabs.

Resulting Pre-Fiscal Distribution

Table 13: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: FY 2017-18 Pre-Fiscal Model ($G_{Pre} = 0.356$)

Decile	Mean Market Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	83,943	3.03%	0.0303	0.0000	0.0303
2	1,21,520	4.38%	0.0741	0.0303	0.1043
3	1,48,559	5.35%	0.1276	0.0741	0.2016
4	1,74,268	6.28%	0.1904	0.1276	0.3180
5	2,01,090	7.25%	0.2629	0.1904	0.4533
6	2,30,984	8.32%	0.3461	0.2629	0.6090
7	2,66,598	9.61%	0.4422	0.3461	0.7883
8	3,12,945	11.28%	0.5550	0.4422	0.9972
9	3,83,446	13.82%	0.6932	0.5550	1.2482
10	8,51,238	30.68%	1.0000	0.6932	1.6932
TOTAL	27,74,593	100%		SUM (Σ):	6.4435

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \quad (9)$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 6.4435 = 1 - 0.6444 \quad (10)$$

$$\boxed{G_{Pre} \approx 0.356} \quad (11)$$

The pre-fiscal Gini coefficient for FY 2017-18 is **0.356**, reflecting higher market inequality compared to the FY 2024-25 estimate of 0.348.

4.2 Construction of the FY 2017-18 Welfare Stack

Scheme-level expenditure actuals are drawn from FY 2016-17, as fiscal outlays in a given year are reflected in household welfare outcomes in the subsequent period, the same period captured by the PLFS 2017-18 survey window (July 2017 to June 2018). Data is sourced from the Expenditure Budget (Union Budget 2018-19) and PRS Legislative Research [PRS Legislative Research, 2018]. For the two components where scheme-level actuals are unavailable at the national level, state-level welfare transfers and public education, GDP-scaled estimates are used. Per-household values for centrally sponsored schemes are

computed over a base of 24 crore welfare-eligible households, consistent with the Helgi Library (2025) estimate of approximately 26.7 crore total households in FY 2017-18[Helgi Library, 2025].

Note: The welfare transfer values employed in this analysis are derived predominantly from aggregate fiscal outlays rather than from household-level receipt data, owing to the absence of comprehensive administrative microdata linking disbursements to individual beneficiaries across all schemes. In practice, the amount that reaches a household may diverge from the per-household outlay estimate due to implementation leakages, administrative overhead, inter-state variation in delivery efficiency, and targeting errors. To the extent that such leakages are systematically higher at the bottom of the distribution, the framework may overstate the welfare gains accruing to the poorest deciles. This limitation is partially mitigated by the use of realised expenditure actuals (rather than budgetary allocations) wherever available, and by the conservative valuation choices adopted throughout, but it cannot be fully resolved without beneficiary-level tracking data, which remains a priority for future iterations of this analysis.

Table 14: FY 2017-18 Welfare Stack: Scheme-Wise Expenditure and Per-Household Value

Scheme	Outlay (₹Cr)	Per HH (₹)	Source / Method
PDS (NFSA)	1,15,145	4,798	Actual
PMAY (Rural + Urban)	27,122	1,130	Actual
LPG Subsidy (DBT only)	13,000	542	Actual (DBT, 2016-17)
MGNREGA	48,215	2,009	Actual
ICDS	15,893	662	Actual
Swachh Bharat Mission	12,619	526	Actual
Mid-Day Meal	9,475	395	Actual
NRLM	3,158	132	Actual
PM-Kisan	0	0	Not launched
PMJAY	0	0	Not launched
JJM	0	0	Not launched
State-Level Welfare	3,16,248	13,177	GDP-scaled + CRISIL haircut
Public Education	2,01,696	8,404	GDP-scaled
TOTAL	7,62,571	31,774	

Several points merit attention:

- **Three schemes absent:** PM-Kisan (launched February 2019), PMJAY (launched September 2018), and the Jal Jeevan Mission (launched August 2019) did not exist in FY 2017-18 and are assigned a welfare value of zero. Together, these three schemes contribute ₹3,476 per household in the FY 2024-25 stack; their absence is the single largest structural difference between the two periods.
- **Fuel subsidies:** In FY 2017-18, cooking fuel support was delivered through the

PAHAL direct benefit transfer scheme, with an actual DBT outlay of ₹13,000 crore (₹542 per household). By FY 2024-25, this was replaced by the targeted Ujjwala scheme (₹12,000 crore for PMUY beneficiaries only). While the headline fuel subsidy envelope was larger in 2017 when under-recoveries are included, the directly transferable household component was smaller and less targeted than the 2024 architecture.

- **State welfare and education:** The state welfare component (₹13,177 per household) is estimated by scaling the FY 2024-25 aggregate of ₹27,777 per household by the ratio of nominal GDP across the two periods (\$2.65 trillion in FY 2017-18 versus \$3.91 trillion in FY 2024-25, ratio = 0.67[World Bank, 2025a]), and applying a CRISIL-based haircut of 0.70 to reflect that state welfare spending as a share of GSDP stood at approximately 1.4% in the pre-2019 period, relative to the 2.0% observed in FY 2025.⁵ The education transfer (₹8,404 per household) is estimated by applying the same GDP scaling ratio to the FY 2024-25 figure of ₹12,400, cross-validated against the Economic Survey 2020-21 and MHRD ABEE 2016-17 actuals [Ministry of Education, 2021].

4.3 Tax Deduction: Old Tax Regime

Under the Old Tax Regime applicable to income earned in FY 2017-18, taxed under Assessment Year 2018-19 (Finance Act 2017) [Ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India, 2017], income tax slabs are as follows: Nil up to ₹2,50,000; 5% from ₹2,50,001 to ₹5,00,000; 20% from ₹5,00,001 to ₹10,00,000; and 30% above ₹10,00,000, with a 3% Education Cess on total tax. Section 87A provides a rebate of ₹2,500 for total incomes not exceeding ₹3,50,000, eliminating tax liability up to a taxable income of ₹3,00,000.

⁵The haircut ratio of 0.70 is derived from the floor of CRISIL Ratings' (2025) reported range of 1.4–1.6% of GSDP for FY 2019 to FY 2024, the earliest available data point. Since the CRISIL dataset does not extend to the pre-2019 period, this floor is adopted as a conservative approximation for FY 2017-18.

Table 15: Statutory Tax Deduction (D_{Tax}): Waterfall Calculation (Old Regime, AY 2018-19)

A. Determination of Taxable Income			
Avg. Market Income (Decile 10)			8,51,238
Less: Section 80C			(-) 1,50,000
Less: Transport Allowance (₹1,600/month)			(-) 19,200
Less: Medical Reimbursement			(-) 15,000
Net Taxable Income			6,67,038
B. Slab-wise Calculation (Waterfall)			
Income Slab	Tax Rate	Taxable Amount	Tax Due (₹)
0 – 2,50,000	Nil	2,50,000	0
2,50,001 – 5,00,000	5%	2,50,000	12,500
5,00,001 – 6,67,038	20%	1,67,038	33,408
		Base Tax Liability	45,908
		Add: Education Cess (3%)	+ 1,377
		Total Tax Deduction (D_{Tax})	47,285

Note: Calculated under the Old Tax Regime (AY 2018-19), Finance Act 2017. Section 87A rebate of ₹2,500 is not applicable as D10 GTI of ₹8,51,238 exceeds the ₹3,50,000 eligibility ceiling. Transport allowance of ₹1,600/month (₹19,200/year) applies from AY 2016-17 onward. Applied exclusively to Decile 10.

4.4 Post-Fiscal Distribution and Gini Coefficient

Welfare transfers are distributed across deciles using the Inverse-MPCE method (identical to the FY 2024-25 methodology). The welfare shares are calculated inversely to consumption, with Decile 10 statutorily excluded from the welfare pool. The post-fiscal “Lived Income” for each decile is computed as:

$$Y_i^{post} = Y_i^{pre} + W_i - T_i$$

where W_i is the welfare transfer and T_i is the tax liability for decile i .

Table 16: Consolidated Fiscal Impact: Market vs. Lived Income (FY 2017-18)

Decile	Pre-Intervention Market Income	Net Fiscal Intervention	Post-Intervention Lived Income	Net Change (%)
1	₹83,943	+ ₹59,036	₹1,42,980	+70.3%
2	₹1,21,520	+ ₹43,713	₹1,65,234	+36.0%
3	₹1,48,559	+ ₹37,261	₹1,85,820	+25.1%
4	₹1,74,268	+ ₹32,731	₹2,06,998	+18.8%
5	₹2,01,090	+ ₹29,046	₹2,30,136	+14.4%
6	₹2,30,984	+ ₹25,799	₹2,56,784	+11.2%
7	₹2,66,598	+ ₹22,715	₹2,89,313	+8.5%
8	₹3,12,945	+ ₹19,602	₹3,32,546	+6.3%
9	₹3,83,446	+ ₹16,061	₹3,99,507	+4.2%
10	₹8,51,238	- ₹47,285	₹8,03,953	-5.6%

Methodology Note: Welfare transfers are distributed based on Inverse MPCE Weighting (HCES 2022-23), targeting the bottom 90% progressively. Decile 10 is the sole net payer of Direct Taxes (AY 2018-19 regime). This fiscal structure yields a final Gini Coefficient of 0.285.

Having established the Lived Income for each decile, we now construct the Lorenz Curve and derive the post-fiscal Gini using the Trapezoidal Rule.

Table 17: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: Final Targeted Model ($G_{Net} = 0.285$)

Decile	Mean Lived Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	1,42,980	4.74%	0.0474	0.0000	0.0474
2	1,65,234	5.48%	0.1023	0.0474	0.1497
3	1,85,820	6.17%	0.1640	0.1023	0.2662
4	2,06,998	6.87%	0.2326	0.1640	0.3966
5	2,30,136	7.64%	0.3090	0.2326	0.5417
6	2,56,784	8.52%	0.3942	0.3090	0.7033
7	2,89,313	9.60%	0.4903	0.3942	0.8845
8	3,32,546	11.04%	0.6006	0.4903	1.0909
9	3,99,507	13.26%	0.7332	0.6006	1.3338
10	8,03,953	26.68%	1.0000	0.7332	1.7332
TOTAL	30,13,272	100%		SUM (Σ):	7.1473

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \quad (12)$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 7.1473 = 1 - 0.7147 \quad (13)$$

$$\boxed{G \approx 0.285} \quad (14)$$

The **Post-Fiscal Lived Income Gini for FY 2017-18 is 0.285**, representing a reduction of 19.8% from the pre-fiscal Gini of 0.356.

5. Historical Benchmark: Estimating the Lived Income Gini for FY 2014-15

The temporal analysis is extended to FY 2014-15 to establish a pre-reform baseline for India's welfare architecture. Three features make this year particularly suited for comparison. First, it sits immediately before a cluster of structural fiscal reforms that transformed both the delivery and scope of public welfare between 2015 and 2017: the nationwide roll-out of the PAHAL direct benefit transfer for LPG, the launch of the Swachh Bharat Mission, the restructuring of Centrally Sponsored Schemes following the Fourteenth Finance Commission award, and the eventual introduction of GST. Second, the National Food Security Act, enacted in September 2013, had not yet achieved full operationalisation across all states by FY 2014-15, placing this year in the transitional phase between the old Targeted Public Distribution System and the universal entitlement framework that followed. Third, the income tax regime in force for AY 2015-16 levied a first-slab rate of 10% on incomes between ₹2,50,001 and ₹5,00,000, double the 5% rate introduced from FY 2017-18 onward, producing a distinct fiscal extraction profile at the top of the distribution.

One data constraint distinguishes the FY 2014-15 estimation from the later periods. The Periodic Labour Force Survey was inaugurated only in 2017-18; no equivalent earnings microdata exists for FY 2014-15. The log-normal mean (μ) for this period is therefore estimated by scaling back the PLFS-anchored μ for FY 2017-18 in proportion to nominal per capita GDP growth over the intervening period.

5.1 Calibration of the Income Distribution

Log-Normal Parameters (μ, σ)

In the absence of PLFS microdata for FY 2014-15, μ is estimated by scaling back the locked FY 2017-18 value ($\mu = 12.28$) using the ratio of nominal GDP per capita across the two periods (\$1,554 in FY 2014-15 versus \$1,950 in FY 2017-18, sourced from World Bank national accounts data [World Bank, 2025b]):

$$\mu_{2014} = \mu_{2017} + \ln\left(\frac{\text{GDP per capita}_{2014}}{\text{GDP per capita}_{2017}}\right) = 12.28 + \ln(0.7969) = 12.28 - 0.227 \approx 12.05$$

This yields a mean annual household income of approximately ₹1,71,099, consistent with the lower wage levels prevailing prior to the acceleration in formal employment and the rise in female workforce participation that characterised the post-2017 period. The standard deviation (σ) is held at 0.55.

Pareto Parameters (α, x_m)

The regime threshold x_m is set at the 90th percentile of the log-normal household income distribution, consistent with the methodology adopted for FY 2024-25 and FY 2017-18. For FY 2014-15, $x_m = \exp(12.05 + 0.55 \times 1.2816) \approx ₹3,46,000$.

The Pareto shape parameter is set at $\alpha = 1.88$, derived by applying the household compression multiplier ($4/3 \approx 1.33$) to the individual-level α estimated from Income Tax Return statistics for AY 2015-16 [Central Board of Direct Taxes, 2016]. The individual α is estimated as the local inter-bracket Pareto exponent between the ₹25 lakh and ₹50 lakh income brackets of the ITR distribution, yielding $\alpha_{indiv} \approx 1.414$. After applying the household compression multiplier, this yields an effective household $\alpha \approx 1.414 \times 4/3 \approx 1.88$.

Resulting Pre-Fiscal Distribution

Table 18: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: FY 2014-15 Pre-Fiscal Model ($G_{Pre} = 0.371$)

Decile	Mean Market Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	66,696	2.94%	0.0294	0.0000	0.0294
2	96,552	4.26%	0.0720	0.0294	0.1014
3	1,18,035	5.21%	0.1241	0.0720	0.1961
4	1,38,462	6.11%	0.1851	0.1241	0.3092
5	1,59,773	7.05%	0.2556	0.1851	0.4407
6	1,83,525	8.09%	0.3365	0.2556	0.5921
7	2,11,821	9.34%	0.4300	0.3365	0.7665
8	2,48,645	10.97%	0.5396	0.4300	0.9696
9	3,04,661	13.44%	0.6740	0.5396	1.2136
10	7,39,182	32.60%	1.0000	0.6740	1.6740
TOTAL	22,67,352	100%		SUM (Σ):	6.2926

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \quad (15)$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 6.2926 = 1 - 0.6293 \quad (16)$$

$$\boxed{G_{Pre} \approx 0.371} \quad (17)$$

5.2 Construction of the FY 2014-15 Welfare Stack

Scheme-level expenditure actuals are drawn from FY 2013-14, following the same lagged-outlay logic employed in the FY 2017-18 estimation. Data is sourced from the Expenditure Budget (Union Budget 2015-16) [Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2015]. Per-household values for centrally sponsored schemes are computed over a base of 23 crore welfare-eligible households, consistent with the Helgi Library (2025) estimate of approximately 25.4 crore total households in FY 2014-15 [Helgi Library, 2025]. State-level welfare and public education are GDP-scaled with source-based haircuts as detailed below.

Note: The LPG and kerosene subsidy figure (₹2,580 crore) reflects only the direct household transfer component and does not include the under-recovery compensation paid to oil marketing companies, consistent with the DBT-only treatment adopted for FY 2017-18. The PAHAL scheme was in early rollout during FY 2014-15 and kerosene DBT was negligible; the ₹2,580 crore figure captures the direct PDS-channel component only.

Table 19: FY 2014-15 Welfare Stack: Scheme-Wise Expenditure and Per-Household Value

Scheme	Outlay (₹Cr)	Per HH (₹)	Source / Method
PDS (TPDS/NFSA)	92,000	4,000	Actual
IAY + RAY (Housing)	13,688	595	Actual
LPG + Kerosene (DBT)	2,580	112	Actual (conservative)
MGNREGA	32,993	1,434	Actual
ICDS	16,363	711	Actual
Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan	11,935	519	Actual
Mid-Day Meal	6,449	280	Actual
NRLM	2,022	88	Actual
PM-Kisan	0	0	Not launched
PMJAY	0	0	Not launched
JJM	0	0	Not launched
Ujjwala	0	0	Not launched
State-Level Welfare	2,00,054	8,698	GDP-scaled + NITI haircut
Public Education	1,48,810	6,470	GDP-scaled
TOTAL	5,26,894	22,908	

Several features of this welfare stack merit attention.

- **Four schemes absent:** PM-Kisan (launched February 2019), PMJAY (launched September 2018), JJM (launched August 2019), and Ujjwala (launched May 2016) did not exist in FY 2014-15 and are assigned zero. Together, they represent a deliberate post-2016 expansion into farmer income support, secondary healthcare, piped water, and targeted fuel access.
- **State welfare and education:** The state welfare component (₹8,698 per household) is estimated by applying the GDP scaling ratio (FY 2014-15/FY 2024-25 = \$2.04T/\$3.91T = 0.5218) to the FY 2024-25 aggregate of ₹27,777, with a haircut of 0.60 derived from the NITI Aayog (2023) analysis of state social sector expenditure [Kumar et al., 2023], which places the welfare-specific component at approximately 1.2% of GSDP in FY 2014-15 relative to CRISIL's reported 2.0% for FY 2025.⁶ The education transfer (₹6,470 per household) applies the same GDP scaling ratio to the FY 2024-25 figure of ₹12,400, without an additional haircut, consistent with the avoided-cost methodology that underpins the education transfer valuation.
- **PDS in transition:** The food subsidy outlay of ₹92,000 crore reflects the TPDS in its pre-NFSA form, covering approximately 65% of the population. The per-household PDS transfer of ₹4,000 compares with ₹4,798 in FY 2017-18 and ₹8,671 in FY 2024-25 – a trajectory that reflects progressive universalisation and the eventual elimination of the Central Issue Price under PMGKAY.
- **Housing in early stage:** The combined Indira Awaas Yojana and Rajiv Awaas Yojana outlay of ₹13,688 crore was subsequently consolidated and scaled up as PMAY, reaching ₹27,122 crore in FY 2016-17 and ₹41,000 crore in FY 2024-25.

5.3 Tax Deduction: Old Tax Regime (AY 2015-16)

Under the Old Tax Regime applicable to income earned in FY 2014-15, taxed under Assessment Year 2015-16, income tax slabs are as follows: Nil up to ₹2,50,000; 10% from ₹2,50,001 to ₹5,00,000; 20% from ₹5,00,001 to ₹10,00,000; and 30% above ₹10,00,000, with a 3% Education Cess. Section 87A provides a rebate of ₹2,000 for total incomes not exceeding ₹5,00,000.

⁶The three-period haircut trajectory is: $1.2\%/2.0\% = 0.60$ for FY 2014-15 (NITI Aayog, 2023); $1.4\%/2.0\% = 0.70$ for FY 2017-18 (CRISIL floor); and 1.00 for FY 2024-25 (CRISIL direct). This monotonically increasing sequence is consistent with the progressive expansion of state welfare spending as a share of GSDP over the decade.

Table 20: Statutory Tax Deduction (D_{Tax}): Waterfall Calculation (Old Regime, AY 2015-16)

A. Determination of Taxable Income			
Avg. Market Income (Decile 10)			7,39,182
Less: Section 80C			(-) 1,50,000
Less: Transport Allowance (₹800/month)			(-) 9,600
Less: Medical Reimbursement			(-) 15,000
Net Taxable Income			5,64,582
B. Slab-wise Calculation (Waterfall)			
Income Slab	Tax Rate	Taxable Amount	Tax Due (₹)
0 – 2,50,000	Nil	2,50,000	0
2,50,001 – 5,00,000	10%	2,50,000	25,000
5,00,001 – 5,64,582	20%	64,582	12,916
		Base Tax Liability	37,916
		Add: Education Cess (3%)	+ 1,137
		Total Tax Deduction (D_{Tax})	39,054

Note: Calculated under the Old Tax Regime (AY 2015-16). Section 87A rebate of ₹2,000 is not applicable as D10 GTI of ₹7,39,182 exceeds the ₹5,00,000 eligibility ceiling. Applied exclusively to Decile 10.

5.4 Post-Fiscal Distribution and Gini Coefficient

Welfare transfers are distributed using the Inverse-MPCE method, with Decile 10 excluded from the welfare pool. The post-fiscal Lived Income for each decile is:

$$Y_i^{post} = Y_i^{pre} + W_i - T_i$$

Table 21: Consolidated Fiscal Impact: Market vs. Lived Income (FY 2014-15)

Decile	Pre-Intervention Market Income	Net Fiscal Intervention	Post-Intervention Lived Income	Net Change (%)
1	₹66,696	+ ₹42,564	₹1,09,260	+63.8%
2	₹96,552	+ ₹31,517	₹1,28,069	+32.6%
3	₹1,18,035	+ ₹26,865	₹1,44,900	+22.8%
4	₹1,38,462	+ ₹23,598	₹1,62,060	+17.0%
5	₹1,59,773	+ ₹20,942	₹1,80,714	+13.1%
6	₹1,83,525	+ ₹18,601	₹2,02,126	+10.1%
7	₹2,11,821	+ ₹16,377	₹2,28,199	+7.7%
8	₹2,48,645	+ ₹14,133	₹2,62,778	+5.7%
9	₹3,04,661	+ ₹11,580	₹3,16,241	+3.8%
10	₹7,39,182	− ₹39,054	₹7,00,128	−5.3%

Methodology Note: Welfare transfers distributed using Inverse MPCE Weighting (HCES 2022-23). Decile 10 is the sole net payer of direct taxes (AY 2015-16). All deciles D1–D9 bear zero tax liability after standard deductions of ₹1,74,600. This fiscal structure yields a final **Gini Coefficient of 0.306**.

Table 22: Gini Coefficient Derivation Matrix: FY 2014-15 Post-Fiscal Model ($G_{Net} = 0.306$)

Decile	Mean Lived Income (₹)	Income Share (%)	Cum. Share (Y_i)	Prev. Share (Y_{i-1})	Trapezoid Sum ($Y_i + Y_{i-1}$)
1	1,09,260	4.49%	0.0449	0.0000	0.0449
2	1,28,069	5.26%	0.0975	0.0449	0.1424
3	1,44,900	5.95%	0.1570	0.0975	0.2545
4	1,62,060	6.66%	0.2236	0.1570	0.3806
5	1,80,714	7.42%	0.2978	0.2236	0.5214
6	2,02,126	8.30%	0.3808	0.2978	0.6786
7	2,28,199	9.37%	0.4746	0.3808	0.8554
8	2,62,778	10.79%	0.5825	0.4746	1.0571
9	3,16,241	12.99%	0.7124	0.5825	1.2949
10	7,00,128	28.76%	1.0000	0.7124	1.7124
TOTAL	24,34,474	100%		SUM (Σ):	6.9422

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i (Y_i + Y_{i-1}) \quad (18)$$

$$G = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n (0.1)(Y_i + Y_{i-1}) = 1 - 0.1 \times 6.9422 = 1 - 0.6942 \quad (19)$$

$$\boxed{G_{Net} \approx 0.306} \quad (20)$$

The **Post-Fiscal Lived Income Gini for FY 2014-15 is 0.306**, representing a reduction of 17.5% from the pre-fiscal Gini of 0.371.

6. Robustness Check: Delivery-Adjusted Lived Income

The baseline specification assumes full delivery of the imputed welfare value, treating every rupee of fiscal expenditure as translating entirely into household command over resources. In practice, administrative friction, supply-chain losses, targeting errors, and implementation gaps attenuate the effective value reaching beneficiary households. This section tests the robustness of the baseline Gini estimates under varying delivery assumptions across all three temporal benchmarks.

Choice of Effective Incidence Ratio

The effective incidence ratio λ captures the proportion of the national average welfare value per household that translates into effective household command. Three scenarios are considered for each period.

For **FY 2024-25**, the BlueKraft Digital Foundation assessment (2025) [Bhat, 2025] reports a composite Welfare Efficiency Index of 0.91 for 2023, reflecting systemic improvements in leakage reduction, subsidy rationalisation, and beneficiary coverage under the DBT architecture. A pessimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.80$ and an optimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.95$ bracket the central estimate.

For **FY 2017-18**, the DBT architecture was operational but not yet mature: PAHAL had been nationally rolled out, Aadhaar seeding of beneficiary databases was underway, and several large schemes (MGNREGA, PDS) still operated through legacy delivery channels with documented leakages. A central estimate of $\lambda = 0.50$ is adopted, consistent with the mid-point of welfare efficiency prior to the full consolidation of the DBT infrastructure. A pessimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.42$ and an optimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.60$ bracket this estimate.

For **FY 2014-15**, welfare delivery was at its thinnest: the PAHAL scheme had just launched in select districts, Aadhaar coverage was incomplete, and state-level schemes operated with substantial administrative overhead and targeting errors. A central estimate of $\lambda = 0.32$ is adopted, reflecting the pre-DBT baseline. A pessimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.25$ and an optimistic bound of $\lambda = 0.40$ bracket this estimate.

Methodology

Under each scenario, the national average welfare value per household is multiplied by λ to obtain the delivery-adjusted average. The adjusted pool is then distributed across

Deciles 1 through 9 using inverse-MPCE weights, preserving the progressive structure of the transfer system. Decile 10 bears the full statutory tax liability under all specifications.

Results

Table 23: Effective Incidence Ratio Sensitivity: Post-Fiscal Gini Estimates Across Three Periods

Period	Scenario	λ	Adjusted Welfare per HH (₹)	Post-Fiscal Gini	Reduction from Pre-Fiscal
FY 2014-15	Pessimistic	0.25	5,727	0.347	6.5%
	Central	0.32	7,331	0.343	7.6%
	Optimistic	0.40	9,163	0.338	8.8%
	Full delivery	1.00	22,908	0.306	17.5%
FY 2017-18	Pessimistic	0.42	13,345	0.319	10.3%
	Central	0.50	15,887	0.314	11.6%
	Optimistic	0.60	19,064	0.308	13.3%
	Full delivery	1.00	31,774	0.285	19.8%
FY 2024-25	Pessimistic	0.80	50,509	0.275	20.8%
	Central	0.91	57,454	0.268	22.9%
	Optimistic	0.95	59,979	0.265	23.7%
	Full delivery	1.00	63,136	0.262	24.7%

Note: Pre-fiscal Gini coefficients are 0.371 (FY 2014-15), 0.356 (FY 2017-18), and 0.348 (FY 2024-25). Reductions are computed relative to these baselines. Central λ values for all three periods are drawn from the BlueKraft Digital Foundation Welfare Efficiency Index [Bhat, 2025]: 0.32 (FY 2014-15), 0.50 (FY 2017-18), and 0.91 (FY 2024-25), reflecting the progressive maturation of India's welfare delivery infrastructure over the decade.

Interpretation

Three findings emerge from the delivery-adjusted analysis.

First, under the central delivery estimate, the post-fiscal Gini for each period is:

$$\boxed{G_{central}^{2014} \approx 0.343 \quad G_{central}^{2017} \approx 0.314 \quad G_{central}^{2024} \approx 0.268} \quad (21)$$

Second, the **trajectory of improvement is preserved** under all delivery assumptions. Regardless of the λ chosen, the post-fiscal Gini declines monotonically across the three periods, confirming that the structural finding of progressive redistribution deepening is not an artefact of the full-delivery assumption.

Third, the **sensitivity band narrows dramatically over time**. In FY 2014-15, the gap between the pessimistic ($\lambda = 0.25$) and full-delivery ($\lambda = 1.00$) specifications is 4.1

Gini points (0.347 vs 0.306). By FY 2024-25, this gap narrows to 1.3 points (0.275 vs 0.262). This compression directly reflects the decade-long improvement in welfare delivery efficiency: as the DBT architecture matured, the divergence between notional and effective welfare incidence narrowed substantially, making the post-fiscal Gini estimate increasingly robust to delivery assumptions.

Table 24: Summary: Pre-Fiscal, Full-Delivery, and Delivery-Adjusted Central Gini Coefficients

Period	$\lambda_{central}$	Pre-Fiscal	Full Delivery	Central Adjusted
FY 2014-15	0.32	0.371	0.306	0.343
FY 2017-18	0.50	0.356	0.285	0.314
FY 2024-25	0.91	0.348	0.262	0.268

The full-delivery specification captures the notional value of the welfare architecture under complete incidence. The central delivery-adjusted specification provides a more conservative estimate of effective household incidence after accounting for delivery attenuation. Under both specifications, and across all three periods, the post-fiscal Gini declines monotonically, and the compression ratio strengthens over time. The progressive narrowing of the sensitivity band from 4.1 points in FY 2014-15 to 1.3 points in FY 2024-25 is itself evidence of the institutional maturation of India’s welfare delivery architecture over the decade.

7. Three-Period Comparison: FY 2014-15 vs FY 2017-18 vs FY 2024-25

Figure 4: Pre-Fiscal, Post-Fiscal and Delivery Adjusted Gini Comparison

Table 25: Headline Comparison: Fiscal Incidence Across Three Periods

Metric	FY 2014-15	FY 2017-18	FY 2024-25
μ (Log-Normal Mean)	12.05	12.28	12.74
α (Pareto Shape)	1.88	2.05	2.16
x_m (P90 Threshold)	₹3,46,000	₹4,36,000	₹6,90,000
Household Base (Crore)	23	24	27
Average Welfare per Household (₹)	22,908	31,774	63,136
Pre-Fiscal Gini	0.371	0.356	0.348
Post-Fiscal Gini	0.306	0.285	0.262
Gini Reduction	17.5%	19.8%	24.7%

Four findings emerge from the three-period comparison.

- 1. Market inequality declined steadily across the decade.** The pre-fiscal Gini fell from 0.371 to 0.356 to 0.348, a cumulative decline of 2.3 points over ten years. The thinning of the Pareto tail (α rising from 1.88 to 2.05 to 2.16) accounts for a substantial share of this compression as the tax base widened through the roll-out of GST, expansion of digital payment infrastructure, and increased formal employment, extreme top-tail concentration moderated progressively across all three periods.
- 2. The welfare architecture expanded in both scope and depth.** The per-household welfare transfer grew from ₹22,908 to ₹31,774 to ₹63,136, at a compound annual rate of 10.7% over the decade. This expansion was not merely a consequence of GDP growth; it reflected deliberate programmatic deepening. Notably, the bulk of the welfare expansion occurred in the second sub-period: the per-household transfer grew by 38.7% between FY 2014-15 and FY 2017-18, and by 98.7% between FY 2017-18 and FY 2024-25.
- 3. The redistribution ratio strengthened progressively and accelerated in the second sub-period.** The proportional Gini reduction rose from 17.5% to 19.8% to 24.7% across the three periods. This progressive strengthening of the redistribution ratio, achieved even as the base level of market inequality was itself declining (making further compression structurally harder), indicates that the fiscal architecture was being actively calibrated rather than merely scaled.

8. Cross-Country Comparative Analysis of Post-Fiscal Inequality Indices

The post-fiscal Gini coefficient estimated in this study permits a structured comparison with disposable-income inequality measures reported for other major economies. Such comparisons must be interpreted with care, since the income concepts, data architectures, and welfare delivery mechanisms differ across national contexts. Nevertheless, the exercise is instructive insofar as it situates India's redistributive effort within a global distributional frame.

8.1 The United States: Cash Transfers and Residual Disparity

The United States records a disposable-income Gini coefficient in the range of 0.39 to 0.41 after accounting for federal and state income taxes, social security transfers, the Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program (SNAP), and refundable tax credits such as the Earned Income Tax Credit (EITC). Despite operating the largest fiscal apparatus in absolute terms, the United States achieves a comparatively modest degree of distributional compression, in part because its transfer architecture is predominantly cash-based and subject to means-testing thresholds that exclude a substantial segment of the lower-middle distribution.

India's welfare architecture operates through a structurally distinct channel. The predominance of in-kind provisioning (subsidised food grains, public healthcare, government schooling, housing assistance, and cooking fuel support) directly substitutes for private market expenditure at the household level, effectively decommodifying a basket of essential consumption goods. This design insulates lower-income households from market price volatility to a degree that cash-transfer systems, which expose beneficiaries to retail price fluctuations, do not. The lower post-fiscal Gini observed for India relative to the United States is therefore attributable not only to the scale of transfers but also to the compositional structure of the welfare instrument: direct provisioning compresses the consumption distribution more tightly than equivalent-value cash disbursements when the price elasticity of essential goods is low.

8.2 Germany: Comparable Compression, Divergent Welfare Levels

The post-fiscal Gini of 0.262 estimated in this study falls below Germany's OECD-reported disposable-income Gini of 0.294. This proximity warrants careful interpretation along two dimensions.

First, the comparison is informative with respect to the *magnitude of distributional compression*. Germany's pre-fiscal market income Gini of approximately 0.49 is compressed by nearly 40 per cent through a combination of progressive income taxation, universal healthcare provision, Kindergeld (child benefits), and pension transfers. India's pre-fiscal Gini of 0.348 is compressed by 24.7 per cent through its own fiscal architecture. In proportional terms, Germany's redistributive effort remains substantially greater. However,

the absolute post-fiscal outcomes converge to a narrower band than the pre-fiscal starting points would suggest, indicating that India's welfare system, while operating at a fraction of Germany's per-capita fiscal capacity, achieves a non-trivial degree of relative compression.

Second, the comparison is *not* informative with respect to absolute welfare. The Gini coefficient is a measure of relative dispersion and is invariant to the level of the distribution. Two economies may exhibit identical Gini coefficients while differing by an order of magnitude in the material standard of living afforded at every point of their respective distributions. The post-fiscal Gini comparison should accordingly be read as evidence that India's fiscal system produces a degree of distributional compression that is quantitatively comparable to that of an advanced European welfare state, not as a claim of equivalent welfare outcomes.

8.3 Interpretive Implications

Three observations emerge from this comparative exercise. First, the post-fiscal Gini of 0.262, when situated alongside the disposable-income Gini coefficients of OECD economies, indicates that India's welfare architecture produces distributional outcomes that are no longer characteristic of a typical developing economy with minimal state intervention. The fiscal system absorbs a measurable share of market disparity before it translates into household consumption.

Second, the compositional structure of India's welfare transfers (predominantly in-kind rather than cash-based) may account for a degree of consumption stabilisation that is not fully captured by cross-country comparisons with cash-transfer-dominant systems. The avoided-cost channel through which in-kind transfers operate compresses the consumption distribution directly, bypassing the savings and expenditure discretion that attenuates the equalising effect of cash transfers.

Third, whether this measured compression in relative dispersion translates into proportionate improvements in multidimensional welfare outcomes, encompassing health status, educational attainment, economic mobility, and the quality of public service delivery, remains an open empirical question. The Gini coefficient captures the shape of the distribution but is silent on the adequacy of the welfare floor or the depth of capability deprivation at any given point. Subsequent research linking the post-fiscal income distribution to non-monetary welfare indicators would provide the evidentiary basis for a more comprehensive assessment of the Indian fiscal system's contribution to human development.

9. Limitations and Interpretive Precautions

The estimation framework developed in this study operates within a set of structural constraints imposed by the prevailing data environment, the parametric modelling choices, and the boundaries of observable fiscal incidence. This section documents these constraints to enable the reader to calibrate the precision with which the findings should be interpreted.

9.1 Hybrid Data Architecture

The income distribution is constructed by combining two independent data systems: the Periodic Labour Force Survey for the bottom 90 per cent and Income Tax Return statistics for the top decile. This design was adopted because no single Indian dataset spans the full income distribution with adequate fidelity at both extremes; household surveys suffer from well-documented right-truncation bias among high earners, while administrative tax records exclude the large informal workforce. The stitching of these two regimes at the 90th percentile is accordingly a modelling convention rather than an empirically observed structural break. Future iterations would benefit from examining alternative cutoff specifications to confirm distributional stability.

9.2 Individual-to-Household Aggregation

The conversion of individual-level PLFS earnings into household-level market income employs a baseline earner-pooling multiplier of 1.92, derived from the product of average household size, adult population share, and the worker-population ratio. This nationally representative parameter is applied uniformly across Deciles 1 through 9. The uniform application therefore introduces a degree of distributional smoothing, and the pre-fiscal Gini of 0.348 should be interpreted as conditional on this particular aggregation convention. Alternative multiplier specifications would shift the baseline and, to some extent, the magnitude of the post-fiscal compression, though not its direction.

9.3 Pareto Tail Estimation and Compression Multiplier

The Pareto shape parameter (α) governing the top decile is estimated at the individual level from ITR statistics using the local inter-bracket Pareto exponent between the ₹25 lakh and ₹50 lakh income brackets, and subsequently adjusted to the household unit of analysis through a household compression multiplier of approximately $4/3$ (≈ 1.33). The estimation bracket is selected because it represents the segment of the upper tail where the power-law relationship is most stable: below ₹25 lakhs, the local exponent is inflated by the log-normal/Pareto transition zone, while above ₹50 lakhs, it collapses below 1.0 as extreme-tail capital income dynamics dominate. While this approach is consistent with the Generalised Pareto Interpolation technique employed in the DINA

framework, the actual tail behaviour between x_m and ₹25 lakhs exhibits varying local values. The compression multiplier of 4/3 is thus a calibration assumption rather than an econometrically estimated parameter; its directional logic is consistent with Gaillard, Hellwig, Wangner, and Werquin (2023)[Gaillard et al., 2023], but its precise magnitude warrants formal sensitivity testing. The resulting household α values should accordingly be read as reflecting a specific and documented conversion assumption.

9.4 Fiscal Outlay as a Proxy for Household Receipt

Welfare transfers in the FY 2024-25 estimation are valued, wherever feasible, using scheme-level per-household averages derived from reported beneficiary counts, actual claims data, and programme-specific coverage statistics. This approach substantially reduces the attribution gap between government outlay and household receipt for the contemporary period. For the historical benchmarks of FY 2014-15 and FY 2017-18, however, comparable beneficiary-level data is either unavailable or incomplete for several schemes, necessitating the use of aggregate fiscal outlays divided by the eligible household base as the welfare valuation method. Government outlay figures in these earlier periods embed components that do not translate directly into household consumption, including administrative overheads, logistics costs, and institutional running expenses. The baseline specification for all three periods assumes full delivery ($\lambda = 1.0$), while the robustness analysis in Section 7 tests delivery-adjusted scenarios calibrated to period-specific welfare efficiency proportions. The reader is accordingly encouraged to treat the delivery-adjusted central estimates as the operationally realistic specification, particularly for the pre-2019 periods where the distance between fiscal outlay and effective household receipt is structurally wider.

9.5 State-Level Welfare Estimation

The state-level welfare transfer of ₹27,777 per household constitutes approximately 44 per cent of the consolidated welfare stack in FY 2024-25. This figure is derived by extrapolating aggregate social welfare expenditure reported by CRISIL Ratings for the top 18 states to a national total, supplemented by an off-budget adjustment informed by RBI State Finances data. The extrapolation was necessitated by the absence of a consolidated, scheme-level fiscal database covering all state governments. However, the definition of “social welfare spending” at the state level is sufficiently broad to encompass departmental salaries, administrative infrastructure, and institutional capital expenditure that may not flow to households as consumable transfers. This component carries a wider confidence interval than the central government scheme valuations, and the overall Gini is moderately sensitive to its magnitude.

9.6 Uniform Progressive Weighting

The consolidated welfare pool is distributed across Deciles 1 through 9 using an inverse-MPCE weighting mechanism derived from HCES 2022-23 consumption data. This ap-

proach captures the aggregate distributional logic of the Indian welfare architecture but treats the entire pool as a single progressive transfer. In practice, each scheme possesses distinct eligibility criteria, and beneficiary profiles. The study would further benefit from improved estimation accuracy if a scheme-by-scheme incidence analysis is carried out when sufficient beneficiary micro-data is available.

9.7 Aggregated Treatment of the Top Decile

Decile 10 is treated as a single analytical unit with a uniform mean market income and a single statutory tax liability. This decile spans the full range from the 90th percentile threshold to the extreme upper tail of the distribution, and its within-decile variance substantially exceeds that of any other segment. Averaging the tax liability across this group understates the effective burden borne by the top 1 per cent while overstating it for households proximate to the lower boundary. A sub-decile decomposition would yield a more granular fiscal incidence profile, but was not pursued because publicly available ITR statistics do not provide the income-bracket granularity required for reliable sub-decile calibration.

9.8 Static Incidence Framework

The model applies tax rules and welfare transfers to observed market incomes without incorporating behavioural responses. Taxation may influence labour supply, savings behaviour, and income reporting among high-income households, while the availability of welfare transfers may affect labour market participation and consumption decisions among lower-income households. The static framework is standard in fiscal incidence analysis and was adopted because credible estimation of behavioural elasticities in the Indian context would require panel data and quasi-experimental variation outside the scope of this study. The results should accordingly be interpreted.

9.9 Temporal Data Asymmetry

The three-period comparison maintains methodological consistency, but the underlying data environment thins progressively as one moves backward in time. The FY 2024-25 estimation benefits from PLFS microdata, recent ITR statistics, HCES consumption data, and scheme-level expenditure actuals. The FY 2017-18 estimation draws on the inaugural PLFS round but requires GDP-scaled estimates for state welfare and education. The FY 2014-15 estimation predates the PLFS entirely and relies on back-scaled income parameters derived from nominal GDP ratios. The confidence interval around the earlier estimates is correspondingly wider, and the observed trajectory of declining inequality, while directionally robust, carries greater parametric uncertainty in the pre-2017 period.

9.10 Cross-Country Comparability

The numerical proximity between India's post-fiscal Gini of 0.262 and the disposable income Gini coefficients reported for advanced welfare states is presented to situate India's redistributive effort within a global frame. The Gini coefficient, however, is a measure of relative dispersion and it does not capture the absolute level of income, the depth of the welfare floor, or the comprehensiveness of public service provision. Two countries may exhibit similar Gini coefficients while differing profoundly in the material standard of living available to households at every point of the distribution. The comparison across countries should be understood as showing which way redistribution goes, not as saying their welfare systems are equal in size or level.

These precautions do not vitiate the central findings. The direction of the result, that India's fiscal architecture produces substantial and progressive compression of market inequality, is robust across delivery assumptions, temporal benchmarks, and distributional specifications. What the precautions establish is the interpretive frame within which the estimates acquire their proper meaning: they are disciplined approximations of fiscal incidence constructed from the strongest available data, not exact measurements of a fixed economic quantity. As India's administrative data infrastructure matures, particularly through unified beneficiary registries, linked tax-transfer records, and more granular sub-national fiscal reporting, subsequent iterations of this framework will be positioned to narrow the confidence intervals documented here.

10. Conclusion

The findings of this study suggest a significant and quantifiable gap between market-generated inequality and the distribution of lived outcomes in India. Across all three temporal benchmarks, the fiscal system produces significant compression: the pre-fiscal Gini fell from 0.371 in FY 2014-15 to 0.348 in FY 2024-25, while the post-fiscal Gini compressed from 0.306 to 0.262 over the same period. The redistribution ratio itself strengthened from 17.5% to 24.7%, indicating that the fiscal architecture deepened faster than the market distribution narrowed.

The findings of this study are suggestive of a possible divergence from the prevailing understanding of a K-shaped resource distribution pattern in the Indian context. Income concentration at the extreme top may indeed be rising, particularly when measured through national accounts frameworks that include retained corporate earnings and unrealised capital gains. For the bottom 90 per cent of households, however, the effective purchasing power is materially strengthened by fiscal intervention, and the degree of that strengthening has increased over the decade.

Future inquiry will need to examine the sustainability of this fiscal trajectory, the extent to which the welfare architecture addresses dimensions of deprivation that extend beyond consumption, and the degree to which behavioural responses may, over time, temper the measured incidence. As India's administrative data architecture becomes more fully institutionalised, particularly through unified beneficiary registries, integrated tax-transfer records, and more granular sub-national fiscal reporting, subsequent iterations of this

framework should be able to generate tighter confidence intervals and support a more comprehensive assessment of multidimensional welfare outcomes.

References

- [Bhalla et al., 2022] Bhalla, S. S., Bhasin, K., and Virmani, A. (2022). Pandemic, poverty, and inequality: Evidence from india. IMF Working Paper No. 2022/069. <https://www.imf.org/-/media/files/publications/wp/2022/english/wpiea2022069-print-pdf.pdf>.
- [Bhat, 2025] Bhat, S. (2025). A quantitative assessment of India’s DBT system. Technical report, BlueKraft Digital Foundation. Released via Press Information Bureau, PRID 2123192, April 2025. Available at: https://www.bluekraft.in/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Shakil-Bhat_DBT-Paper_FNL-paper.pdf.
- [Central Board of Direct Taxes, 2016] Central Board of Direct Taxes (2016). Income tax return statistics: Assessment year 2015-16. Technical report, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. Available at: <https://incometaxindia.gov.in/Documents/Direct%20Tax%20Data/Income-Tax-Statistics-IT-Return-AY-2015-16.pdf>.
- [Central Board of Direct Taxes, 2019] Central Board of Direct Taxes (2019). Income tax return statistics: Assessment year 2018-19. Technical report, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. Gross Total Income distribution across income slabs for all taxpayers. Used for calibration of Pareto shape parameter (α) for FY 2017-18 income distribution. Available at: <https://www.incometaxindia.gov.in/documents/20117/0/IT-Return-Statistics-Assessment-Year-2018-19.pdf/d2fc64ff-cef5-c21c-32c9-8203afbe3172?version=1.0&t=1767685100079>.
- [CRISIL Ratings, 2025] CRISIL Ratings (2025). Social welfare spend of states to stay high at 2 percent of gsdp this fiscal. <https://www.crisilratings.com/en/home/newsroom/press-releases/2025/06/social-welfare-spend-of-states-to-stay-high-at-2percent-of-gsdp-this-fiscal.html>.
- [DD News, 2024] DD News (2024). PMAY-G: Over 2.82 crore rural homes built, target extended to 4.95 crore by 2029. <https://ddnews.gov.in/en/pmay-g-over-2-82-crore-rural-homes-built-target-extended-to-4-95-crore-by-2029/>.
- [DD News, 2025] DD News (2025). Year ender 2025: India strengthens food security and farmer welfare. <https://ddnews.gov.in/en/year-ender2025-india-strengthens-food-security-and-farmer-welfare/>.
- [Department of Rural Development, Government of India, nd] Department of Rural Development, Government of India (n.d.). MGNREGA. https://nrega.dord.gov.in/MGNREGA_new/Nrega_home.aspx.
- [Federal Government of Germany, nd] Federal Government of Germany (n.d.). Gini coefficient of equivalised disposable income. <https://www.gut-leben-in-deutschland.de/indicators/income/gini-coefficient-income/>.
- [Gaillard et al., 2023] Gaillard, A., Hellwig, C., Wangner, P., and Werquin, N. (2023). Consumption, wealth, and income inequality: A tale of tails. Working Paper WP 2023-43, Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago. Revised December 2023. TSE Working Paper No.

- 1493, Toulouse School of Economics. Available at: <https://www.chicagofed.org/-/media/publications/working-papers/2023/wp2023-43.pdf>.
- [Helgi Library, 2025] Helgi Library (2025). Number of households in India. Technical report, Helgi Library. Source: National Statistical Office. 296 million households estimated for 2025. Available at: <https://www.helgilibrary.com/indicators/number-of-households/india/>.
- [Income Tax Department, 2023] Income Tax Department (2023). Income tax return statistics for the AY 2023–24. Technical report. <https://incometaxindia.gov.in/Documents/Direct%20Tax%20Data/Approved-version-Income-Tax-Return-Statistics-for-the-AY-2023-24.pdf>.
- [International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF, 2022] International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and ICF (2022). National family health survey (NFHS-5), 2019–21: India. Technical report, International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai. <https://dhsprogram.com/pubs/pdf/FR375/FR375.pdf>.
- [Kumar et al., 2023] Kumar, A., Nema, A., Hazarika, J., and Sachdeva, H. (2023). Social sector expenditure of states: Pre and post fourteenth finance commission (2014-15 and 2015-16). Technical report, NITI Aayog, Government of India. Analyses state-level social sector expenditure as a percentage of GSDP for FY 2014-15 (actuals) and FY 2015-16 (revised estimates) across all states. Available at: https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2023-02/Social-Sector-Expenditure-of-States_Paper.pdf.
- [Kundu and Cabrera, 2022] Kundu, S. and Cabrera, M. (2022). Fiscal policies and their impact on income distribution in india. Working Paper CEQ WP 120, CEQ Institute, Tulane University. April 2022. Prepared as part of the Commitment to Equity Institute’s country-cases research program. Available at: <https://repec.tulane.edu/R/ePEc/ceq/ceq120.pdf>.
- [Lustig, 2018] Lustig, N. (2018). *Commitment to Equity Handbook: Estimating the Impact of Fiscal Policy on Inequality and Poverty*. Brookings Institution Press, Washington, D.C. CEQ Institute, Tulane University. Available at: <https://commitmenttoequity.org/publications-ceq-handbook>.
- [Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare, ovin] Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare (<https://pmkisan.gov.in/>). PM-Kisan Samman Nidhi.
- [Ministry of Education, 2021] Ministry of Education (2021). Analysis of budgeted expenditure on education (ABEE), 2016-17 to 2018-19. Technical report, Planning, Monitoring and Statistics Bureau, Department of Higher Education, Government of India. Available at: https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/statistics-new/Analysis_of_Budgeted_Expenditure_on_Education_2017-2019.pdf.
- [Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2015] Ministry of Finance, Government of India (2015). Expenditure budget volume 1: Statement of budget estimates, union budget 2015-16. Scheme-wise actual expenditure for FY 2013-14 and budget estimates for FY 2014-15 and FY 2015-16. Available at: <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/b>

[udget2015-2016/ub2015-16/eb/allsbse.pdf](#).

[Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2024] Ministry of Finance, Government of India (2024). The finance (no. 2) bill, 2024 (bill no. 55 of 2024). https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/budget2024-25/doc/Finance_Bill.pdf.

[Ministry of Finance, Government of India, 2025] Ministry of Finance, Government of India (2025). Economic survey 2024–25. Technical report, Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. Tabled in Parliament, 31 January 2025. Table 12.1, p. 378. Available at: <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in/budget2025-26/economicsurvey/doc/echapter.pdf>.

[Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2024] Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (2024). Unstarred question no. 1096, Rajya Sabha, session 269. Reply by Minister of State for Health and Family Welfare, Shri Prataprao Jadhav. Available at: https://sansad.in/getFile/annex/269/AU1096_Ea1erz.pdf?source=pqars.

[Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, 2025] Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (2025). Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana – urban. <https://pmay-urban.gov.in/>.

[Ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India, 2017] Ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India (2017). The finance act, 2017 (no. 7 of 2017). An Act to give effect to the financial proposals of the Central Government for the financial year 2017-18. Governs income tax slabs and rates applicable for Assessment Year 2018-19, including the reduction of the first slab rate to 5% and revision of Section 87A rebate to ₹2,500 for total incomes not exceeding ₹3,50,000. Published in the Gazette of India Extraordinary, Part II, Section 1. Available at: <https://egazette.gov.in/WriteReadData/2017/175141.pdf>.

[Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas, 2025] Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas (2025). Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana: About scheme. <https://www.pmuy.gov.in/about.html>.

[Ministry of Rural Development, 2025] Ministry of Rural Development (2025). Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana – NRLM reports. <https://nrlm.gov.in/outerReportAction.do?methodName=showIndex#gsc.tab=0>.

[Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2019] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2019). Annual report: Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS), July 2017 – June 2018. Technical report, National Statistical Office, Government of India. Available at: https://mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Annual_Report_PLFS_2017_18.pdf.

[Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2024a] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2024a). Periodic labour force survey (PLFS): Annual report, July 2023 – June 2024. Technical report, National Statistical Office, Government of India, New Delhi. https://dge.gov.in/dge/sites/default/files/2024-10/Annual_Report_Periodic_Labour_Force_Survey_23_24.pdf.

[Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2024b] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2024b). Periodic labour force survey (PLFS) data.

<https://esankhyiki.mospi.gov.in/macroindicators?product=plfs&tab=table>.

- [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, 2024] Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India (2024). Survey on household consumption expenditure: 2022–23 (nss report no. 591). https://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Report_591_HCES_2022-23New.pdf.
- [National Sample Survey Office, MoSPI, 2025] National Sample Survey Office, MoSPI (2025). Comprehensive modular survey on education – nss 80th round, 2025. https://microdata.gov.in/nada/index.php/catalog/255/data-dictionary/F2?file_name=CMSE80PER25.
- [National Statistical Office, 2022] National Statistical Office (2022). Women and men in india 2022. Technical report, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India. Population statistics chapter reports age-group wise distribution of India’s population. Available at: https://mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/women-men22/PopulationStatistics22.pdf.
- [OECD, nd] OECD (n.d). Income distribution database: Methodological note. <https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/data/methods/QSA-Methodological-Note.pdf>.
- [People Research on India’s Consumer Economy (PRICE), 2016] People Research on India’s Consumer Economy (PRICE) (2016). ICE 360 survey: Are single-earner families different from others? Technical report. <https://www.price360.in/articles-details.php?url=are-singleearner-families-different-from-others>.
- [PM India, 2025] PM India (2025). Cabinet approves the continuation of Swachh Bharat Mission. https://www.pmindia.gov.in/en/news_updates/cabinet-approves-the-continuation-of-swachh-bharat-mission-urban-sbm-u-till-2025-26-for-sustainable-outcomes/.
- [Press Information Bureau, 2024] Press Information Bureau (2024). Cabinet approves extension of Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2210211®=3&lang=2>.
- [Press Information Bureau, 2025a] Press Information Bureau (2025a). PM POSHAN scheme guidelines and allocation. <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2120666®=3&lang=2>.
- [Press Information Bureau, 2025b] Press Information Bureau (2025b). Swachh bharat mission – gramian. Ministry of Jal Shakti, Government of India. Available at: <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2147695>.
- [PRS Legislative Research, 2018] PRS Legislative Research (2018). Union budget 2018-19: Demands for grants analysis. Technical report, PRS Legislative Research, New Delhi. Scheme-wise actual expenditure for FY 2016-17 and revised estimates for FY 2017-18. Available at: https://prsindia.org/files/budget/budget_parliament/2018/Union%20Budget%20-%20Demands%20for%20Grants.pdf.

-
- [PRS Legislative Research, 2024] PRS Legislative Research (2024). Demand for grants 2024-25 analysis: Jal Shakti. Technical report. Available at: https://prsindia.org/files/budget/budget_parliament/2024/DFG_2024-25_Analysis_Jal_Shakti.pdf.
- [PRS Legislative Research, 2026a] PRS Legislative Research (2026a). Demand for grants 2026-27 analysis: Jal Shakti. Technical report. Available at: https://prsindia.org/files/budget/budget_parliament/2026/DfG_Analysis_2026-27-Jal_Shakti.pdf.
- [PRS Legislative Research, 2026b] PRS Legislative Research (2026b). Union budget 2026-27 analysis. Technical report. Table 6: Scheme-wise Allocation (Actuals 2024-25, RE 2025-26, BE 2026-27). Available at: https://prsindia.org/files/budget/budget_parliament/2026/Union_Budget_Analysis-2026-27.pdf.
- [Reserve Bank of India, 2024] Reserve Bank of India (2024). State finances: A study of budgets of 2024–25. <https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/Publications/PDFs/OSTATEFINANCE2024AE6FF65F475C4934B53CC8ABE7FAB30E.PDF>.
- [United Nations Population Fund, 2025] United Nations Population Fund (2025). World population dashboard: India. <https://www.unfpa.org/data/world-population/IN>.
- [World Bank, 2025a] World Bank (2025a). Gdp (current US\$) – india. National Accounts data. Used for nominal GDP scaling of state welfare and education transfer estimates across FY 2014-15, FY 2017-18, and FY 2024-25. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=IN>.
- [World Bank, 2025b] World Bank (2025b). Gdp per capita (current US\$) – india. National Accounts data, 2012–2024. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?end=2024&locations=IN&start=2012>.
- [World Bank, 2025c] World Bank (2025c). Poverty and inequality platform: India country profile. <https://pip.worldbank.org/country-profiles/IND>.
- [World Inequality Database, 2025a] World Inequality Database (2025a). *Distributional National Accounts (DINA) Guidelines 2025: Methods and Concepts*. <https://wid.world/document/distributional-national-accounts-dina-guidelines-2025-methods-and-concepts-used-in-the-world-inequality-database/>.
- [World Inequality Database, 2025b] World Inequality Database (2025b). Germany – world inequality database. <https://wid.world/country/germany/>.
- [World Inequality Database, 2025c] World Inequality Database (2025c). India – world inequality database. <https://wid.world/country/india/>.